

TC FOR BE

TRANSFORMATIVE CHANGE
FOR BIODIVERSITY & EQUITY

Grant agreement number: 101082057

DELIVERABLE D2.1

Report on international biodiversity governance initiatives: Transformative change pathways for biodiversity and equity to inform EU policymakers and agrifood system stakeholders (M12, R, PU)

Lead party for deliverable: WU – Wageningen University
UoG- University of Greenwich NRI

Document type: R

Due date of deliverable: 31-12-2023

Actual submission date: 31-12-2023

Version: 1.0

Dissemination level: Public

Authors: Marina Benitez Kanter (WU), Teresa Sarasa Nagore (WU), Caspar Krampe (WU)

Reviewers: Paul Ingenbleek (WU), Valerie Nelson (UoG), Verina Ingram (WU)

WP	Task	Deliverable	Authors (lead and others)	Participant organisation	Dissemination level	Report Date & Version	Deliverable Delivery (month)	date
2	1	2.1	Paul Ingenbleek	WU, UoG		31102023	31.12.2023	

Partners

LEGAL NOTICE

The information in this document is provided as is and no guarantee or warranty is given that the information is fit for any particular purpose. The user thereof uses the information at its sole risk and liability.

© TCforBE, 2023. Reproduction is authorised provided the source is acknowledged.

Citation: *M. Benitez Kanter, T. Sarasa Nagore, C. Krampe (2023) Report on international biodiversity governance initiatives: Transformative change pathways for biodiversity and equity to inform EU policymakers and agrifood system stakeholders. TcforBE. Wageningen University & Research. Wageningen*

DISCLAIMER

TcforBE is funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are, however, those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA) and can not be held responsible for them.

Contents

Abstract	5
Glossary	5
TCforBE Project Summary	5
Background	6
TCforBE aims and objectives.....	6
TCforBE overall approach.....	8
I. Introduction	10
1.1 Problem statement	10
1.2 Approach	11
1.3 Structure of the report.....	11
2. Methodology.....	12
3. International governance and policy agreements.....	14
3.1. UN Sustainable Development Goals	14
3.2. United Nations initiatives.....	18
3.2.1. FAO's Strategic Framework.....	18
3.2.2. UN Sustainable Food Systems Programme Sustainable Food Systems (SFS) Programme	20
3.2.3 IFAD Strategy on Biodiversity 2022-2025 and Strategy on Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion	20
3.3. World Trade Organization (WTO).....	21
3.4. CBD Post-Global Biodiversity Framework.....	21
3.5. IPBES Global Assessment Report on Biodiversity. United Nations	22
3.6. IPCC Sixth Assessment.....	22
3.7. Summary.....	23
4. European Union policies, laws and regulations related to agrifood systems	27
4.1. European Green Deal.....	27
4.2. The Farm to Fork Strategy (F2F).....	27
4.3. Biodiversity Strategy for 2030	29
4.4. European Union's new Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) (2023-27).....	30
4.3. European Union's Trade Agreements.....	32
Figure 2: Timeline of EU's strategies for establishing EPAs, based on McNeill (2020).	33
4.4. Summary.....	34
5. Private sector initiatives and market mechanisms	36
5.1. Private sector initiatives.....	36
5.2. Private sector cases	38
5.2.1. Certification Schemes	38
5.2.2. Direct Sourcing.....	39
5.2.3. Business ecosystem initiatives and NGOs.....	40
5.2.4. Informative Approaches.....	40
5.2.5. Corporate initiatives	41
5.4 Summary.....	43

6. Civil society & non-governmental organisation initiatives, social and ecological movements	46
6.1. BINGOs.....	46
6.1.1. WWF	46
6.1.2 GreenPeace	46
6.1.3 Friends of the Earth.....	46
6.2. Environmental NGOs.....	47
6.2.1 EnvoVert	47
6.2.2 GRAIN.....	47
6.2.3 ASEED.....	47
6.3. Social Movements	48
6.3.1 La Vía Campesina	48
6.3.2 Slow Food Europe.....	48
6.4. Summary	48
7. Discussion and conclusions.....	51
References	55

Tables

Table 1 The Study Producer Countries and Landscapes	9
Table 2 Key documents analysed.....	12
Table 3 SDGs and targets relevant to biodiversity conservation, equity & sustainable agrifood systems.....	14
Table 4 United Nations instruments and documents promoting agrifood system transformation.	18
Table 5 FAO's strategy on 'Better Lives' in the agrifood system, adapted from FAO (2021)	19
Table 6 Definitions of Biodiversity and Equity in the Actor Group International Policy	25
Table 7 Definitions of Biodiversity and Equity by diverse stakeholders in the European Union governance pathway	35
Table 8 Biodiversity principles and metrics according to Unilever's Regenerative Agriculture Principles (Unilever, 2021)	41
Table 9 Definitions of Biodiversity and Equity in the market and private sector governance pathway	44
Table 10 Definitions of Biodiversity and Equity in the Actor Group NGOs & Civil Society	50

Figures

Figure 1 Components of the TCforBE Project	8
Figure 2 Timeline of EU's strategies for establishing EPAs, based on McNeill (2020)	33

Abstract

The Transformative Change for Biodiversity and Equity (TCforBE) project (2022 – 2026), will support transdisciplinary research to co-generate transformative change pathways in the context of telecoupled agrifood systems. It will engage diverse stakeholders and explore plural perspectives within the EU and partner countries of Cameroon, Colombia, and Kenya, including EU and national policymakers and Indigenous Peoples and local communities. The project aims to strengthen stakeholder capacity on transformative change pathways leading to enhanced biodiversity and equity outcomes. Work package (WP) 2 of the project specifically focuses on the governance pathways that can initiate transformative change from consumer countries, in particular the European Union.

In this first deliverable of work package 2, we aim to identify, characterise and assess the effectiveness of consumer country governance and policy pathways, levers and innovations for transformative change in agrifood systems and trade with high biodiversity outcomes and equity. Drawing on a stakeholder analysis that was completed earlier within the TCforBE project, we describe the way in which the stakeholders contribute to food systems, biodiversity, and equity. Furthermore, we describe levers that the different stakeholders are implementing for producing transformative change towards biodiversity and equity. Finally, we compare the definitions of biodiversity and equity employed by different organisations and stakeholders as a basic condition for effective governance and transformative change towards biodiversity and equity.

In this report, we discuss four domains of EU agrifood governance pathways, which shape the impact of these food systems in EU and internationally, namely (1) international governance & policy initiatives, (2) EU Laws, policies and regulations, (3) Market & private sector mechanisms and initiatives, and (4) social movements and Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs).

The overview provided in this report will serve subsequent tasks of this WP, which will provide a deeper analysis of each of the governance pathways. In combination with WP 1 and WP3, WP2 contributes with envisioning a consumer countries perspective on transformative change of food systems towards biodiversity and equity in producing countries (WP4, WP5).

Glossary

See [TC4BE glossary](#) for key terms and definitions

TCforBE Project Summary

Demand for agricultural commodities from EU agrifood systems is driving land use change in biodiversity-rich countries in the Global South, leading to major biodiversity losses. Globalisation processes have led to increases in EU imports of commodities such as soya and palm oil. EU trade has become increasingly 'telecoupled', i.e. characterised by distant, coupled human and natural systems via highly inequitable global value chains, which have extensive socioeconomic and environmental impacts.

Tackling the EU's global biodiversity footprint is a top EU policy priority. Transformative change pathways are needed for safe and just transitions; but there are plural perspectives on what might constitute transformative change for food territories and systems, including telecoupled ones, and how to achieve it. New EU policies, such as Farm to Fork, may significantly re-shape agrifood trade between the EU and producer countries, with a range of potential implications for employment, livelihoods, but also equity, justice, and biodiversity. Much depends upon the purpose of the food system or territory, but there is contestation on potential food futures at different scales. There are increasing calls for systemic levers, but barriers to action are significant.

The Transformative Change for Biodiversity and Equity (TCforBE) project², (2022 – 2026), will support transdisciplinary research to co-generate transformative change pathways in the context of telecoupled agrifood systems. It will engage diverse stakeholders and explore plural perspectives within the EU and partner countries of Cameroon, Colombia and Kenya, including EU and national policymakers and Indigenous Peoples and local communities. The project aims to strengthen stakeholder capacity on transformative change pathways leading to enhanced biodiversity and equity outcomes.

Underpinned by multi-stakeholder social learning cycles and attention to plural values, the researchers will seek to co-generate and co-analyse transformative change pathways at different scales for highly telecoupled landscapes and to facilitate dialogues between landscape actors and national and EU scales. To inform these learning cycles and dialogues, researcher driven activities will enrich the landscape and national learning processes and contribute to an overall analysis of transformative change pathways in telecoupled contexts. Envisaged research and learning activities include:

- Conceptual work on transformative change and biodiversity and equity pathways in telecoupled food and agriculture contexts, and synthesis and analysis of findings.
- Exploration of plural perspectives on transformative change at EU, national and landscape scales through qualitative research.
- Social learning cycles at landscape scale: participant-driven learning to co-generate transformative change pathways for food systems and territories (creative learning activities) and to inform/reflect upon planned researcher-led activities (e.g. rural imaginaries research, Bayesian tool development, case studies of corporate and regenerative enterprises). Analysis and social learning on plural perspectives on transformative change at national scale and identification of land use change drivers (e.g. commodity impacts, at-risk biodiversity hotspots, and sustainable landscape initiative impacts).
- A global dialogue, facilitated by the Global Landscapes Forum, will link the transdisciplinary processes between the scales, supported by additional dissemination and communication activities.
- Generation of scenarios and modelling of EU agrifood systems transformations.
- Analysis of interconnected processes and levers including EU biodiversity governance, trade, legal, consumer, collective action and sustainable finance levers and social innovations.

Background

TCforBE aims and objectives

Demand for agricultural commodities from EU agrifood systems is driving land use change in biodiversity-rich countries in the Global South, leading to major biodiversity losses. Globalisation processes have led to increases in EU imports of commodities such as soya and palm oil. EU trade has become increasingly 'telecoupled', i.e. characterised by distant, coupled human and natural systems via highly inequitable global value chains, which have extensive socioeconomic and environmental impacts.

Tackling the EU's global biodiversity footprint is a top EU policy priority. Transformative change pathways are needed for safe and just transitions; but there are plural perspectives on what might constitute transformative change for food territories and systems, including telecoupled ones, and on how to achieve it. New EU policies, such as Farm to Fork, may significantly re-shape agrifood trade between the EU and producer countries, with a range of potential implications for employment, livelihoods, but also equity, justice, and biodiversity. Much depends upon the purpose of the food system or territory, but there is contestation on potential food futures at different scales. There are increasing calls for systemic levers, but barriers to action are significant.

The Transformative Change for Biodiversity and Equity (TCforBE) project², (2022 – 2026), will support **transdisciplinary research to co-generate transformative change pathways in the context of telecoupled agrifood systems**. It will engage diverse stakeholders and explore plural perspectives within the EU and partner countries of Cameroon, Colombia, and Kenya, including EU and national policymakers and Indigenous Peoples and local communities. The project aims to strengthen stakeholder capacity on transformative change pathways leading to enhanced biodiversity and equity outcomes.

The project aims to inform policy discourse, e.g. the EU's Green Deal implementation, and especially the Farm to Fork Strategy, which aims to reduce the environmental and climate footprint of the EU food system and its climate resilience, and specifically responds to expert scientific advice that highlights a particular need for more social science evidence on **how to achieve a sustainable food system**. The project will generate such evidence, as well as contributions from and to environmental science on biodiversity measurement and valuation.

The project will also engage national policymakers and seek to inform landscape stewardship strategies in study landscapes in Africa and Latin America.

TCforBE contributes to four HORIZON EUROPE specific outcomes: 1) Sustainable pathways, 2) human dimensions, 3) social norms, behaviours, values, and 4) inform/motivate transformational change. The project work packages (WPs) address all the outcomes in a cross-cutting way and are arranged according to *scale of interest* (e.g. EU and global, national producer countries, landscape levels).

There are seven **work packages** addressing the project's specific objectives (Box 1), each with associated results and deliverables:

- WP 1 will generate insights on EU policies and societal shifts under new green policies in relation to food systems and modelling of potential impacts on relevant biomes.
- WP 2 explores transformative governance arrangements and levers for change. This includes analysis of trade and legal levers, social movements and collective action, and biodiversity governance initiatives, as well as identifying the best ways to engage with EU and other scale learning and communications stakeholders.
- WP 3 will summarise the taxonomy and related regulations targeting and enabling Biodiversity measurement and develop sustainable finance pathways that are aggregable and scalable to impact and transform current mainstream finance logics.
- WP 4 – national scale engagement and research – identification of current visions of future relating to food and territories (Q methodology), followed by social processes and researcher-led activities to co-frame and co-learn on transformative change pathways including generation of scenarios, geospatial mapping of commodity and policy impacts.
- WP 5 – landscape scale engagement and research - activities as in WP4, but the transformative change pathways will include generation of a Bayesian tool drawing on Q methodology and social learning, corporate/regen case studies, rural imaginaries (political ecology and ethnography).
- WP 6 will involve a conceptual framing, but also synthesis of findings and support for inter-landscape and global / EU dialogues on transformative change pathways.
- WP7 concerns management, dissemination and communication of the project.

Box 1: TCforBE Specific Objectives

Objective 1: Deepen understanding and capacity of agrifood policymakers on transformative pathways for biodiversity and equity in EU telecoupled agrifood systems,.

Objective 2: Identify, assess, and engage EU policymakers and stakeholders on demand-side consumer country governance arrangements for transformative change in telecoupled EU agrifood systems for positive biodiversity and equity outcomes.

Objective 3: Analyse and assess the potentials and limitations of existing biodiversity metrics, measurements, and finance levers (EU Action 68) and derive innovative financial instruments to achieve high biodiversity business transformations that are aggregable and scalable to impact and transform current mainstream finance logics (EU Actions 72 and 73).

Objective 4: Identify, co-analyse, and assess, with policymakers and stakeholders, national supply side producer country policies, scenarios and transformative change pathways for biodiversity and equity.

Objective 5: To co-generate transformative change pathways for sustainable and regenerative landscapes, with high biodiversity and equity outcomes, drawing on new evidence and tools on biodiversity imaginaries, commodity impacts, SLI effectiveness/impacts, and corporate/regenerative enterprise.

Objective 6: Synthesise evidence and build global, regional and landscape learning to foster transformative change on biodiversity

All work packages will engage with communications, WP7 has a particular focus on making the knowledge, tools and methods generated by the project available to global audiences through appropriate media, to inform policy dialogues and learning. The transformative change pathways for landscape approaches, will be shared with and disseminated to policymakers, researchers, and agrifood system stakeholders.

TCforBE overall approach.

The overall approach is underpinned by **multi-stakeholder social learning cycles** and ensuring attention is given to plural values. The researchers will seek to cogenerate and co-analyse transformative change pathways at different scales for highly telecoupled landscapes and to facilitate dialogues between landscape actors and national and EU level stakeholders. To inform these learning cycles and dialogues, researcher driven activities will enrich the landscape and national level learning processes and contribute to an overall analysis of transformative change pathways in telecoupled contexts (Figure 1).

Figure 1 Components of the TCforBE Project

The envisaged research and learning activities include:

- Conceptual work on transformative change and biodiversity and equity pathways in telecoupled food and agriculture contexts, and synthesis and analysis of findings.
- Generation of scenarios and modelling of EU agrifood systems transformations. Understanding the potential implications of EU policy and societal transitions for low- and middle-income countries that link to the EU through telecoupling is vital as dietary shifts are already occurring and policy decisions are being made which may reduce or change EU country sourcing patterns.
- Exploration of plural perspectives on transformative change at EU, national and landscape scales through qualitative research.
- Analysis of interconnected processes and levers including EU biodiversity governance, trade, legal, consumer, collective action and sustainable finance levers and social innovations.)
- Analysis and social learning on plural perspectives on transformative change at national scale and identification of land use change drivers (e.g. commodity impacts, at-risk biodiversity hotspots, and sustainable landscape initiative impacts.)
- Social learning cycles at landscape scale: participant-driven learning to co-generate transformative change pathways for food systems and territories (creative learning activities) and to inform/reflect upon planned researcher-led activities.

- A global dialogue, facilitated by the Global Landscapes Forum, will link the transdisciplinary processes between the scales, supported by additional dissemination and communication activities.

Table 1 The Study Producer Countries and Landscapes

Country	Landscapes	Landscape characteristics
Cameroon	Dja-Tridom	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Emerging cocoa agrofood systems export timber and non-timber forest products (NTFP) trade, mining • Medium-high levels of telecoupling • Sustainability landscape initiatives (SLI) e.g. Dja Green cocoa landscape • Large areas of rapidly degrading high-biodiversity forests, increasing agriculture
Colombia	Eastern Plains Llanos Orientales Magdalena River Cauca River	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agricultural expansion for palm oil, cattle ranching, and reforestation programs. • Megadiverse landscapes • 20% in conservation and 30% in communal lands but facing violence, illicit economies, and weak state presence. • Appropriation of public lands, encroachment into natural parks, local elites driving deforestation, displacement of smallholders
Kenya	Mau forest – Masai - Mara river basin	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wetlands - expanding rice production and fish farming, and grasslands with grazing systems • High biodiversity forests, conservation areas • Tea-avocado-fruit-livestock-timber-NTFP-horticulture systems • Medium levels of telecoupling • Large areas of high biodiversity forest ecosystems & extensive agriculture • Regenerative change & SLIs: MaMaSe program
	Mt Kenya	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Grasslands (grazing systems) and tea-fruit-livestock-timber-horticulture systems • High biodiversity forests, conservation areas • Large areas high biodiversity forests, protected areas & extensive agriculture • Medium-high levels of telecoupling • SLIs: Mt Kenya Forest Landscape Restoration

I. Introduction

1.1 Problem statement

Modernised and industrialised food production models are causing environmental, social and economic hazards at multiple levels (Eakin et al., 2014; Laurence, 2019; Willet et al., 2019). It has been estimated that food systems are responsible for approximately 80% of deforestation causing biodiversity loss, and the pollution of soils and water bodies due to the extensive use of pesticides and fertilisers (Butler, 2018; Willet et al., 2019). Moreover, deforestation linked to food production systems such as coffee, tea, cacao, palm oil and beef, is responsible for approximately 23% of greenhouse global emissions (IPCC, 2022). Furthermore, guided by market values, these systems are displacing local production systems and the traditional knowledge for cultivation, promoting the privatisation of communal lands, where in some cases these lands have been expropriated, displacing the local populations from their original territories (Laurence et al., 2019).

To overcome the socio-environmental problems related to the telecoupled value chains is extremely challenging: multiple public and private policies, strategies and actions exist, implemented to transform the food systems towards sustainability. However, there might be different pathways for archiving “equitable” and “biodiverse” food systems transformations according to the different values, roles and power that the actors and the institutions play in the food systems. These diverse values and visions and widespread power inequalities interplay to create contestation over food system transformations.

For example, the new European legislation, the European Green Deal (EU Green Deal) is a comprehensive plan presented by the European Commission in December 2019, aimed at making Europe the world's first climate-neutral continent by 2050 (Willer et al., 2022; European Commission, 2020). In this initiative, the Farm to Fork strategy and the net zero deforestation law “Regulation (EU) 2023/1115”, which entered into force the 29 of June of 2023, aim to promote zero deforestation value chains of deforestation-linked-products such as coffee, cacao, tea, palm oil, beef, etc. (European Commission, 2023).

To reach the targets established by the EU Green Deal, the Farm to Fork Strategy, and Zero Deforestation laws need to provide sufficient food for a growing population of about 10 billion people by 2050 while tackling environmental challenges and social inequalities. For this, policies, strategies, and actions, do not only need to secure Net Zero deforestation value chains, but they also need to promote a deep transformation of food systems, where biodiversity and equity can be secured (Gupta et al., 2023; McDermott et al., 2023). To transform European food systems, not only policy initiatives are necessary, but it is also necessary to understand which are the current actors, institutions and discourses that are playing a major role in defining the European Union's policies and food system governance.¹

To promote effective and influential policies, strategies, and actions, this report gives an overview of the Identification, characterisation and assessment of the effectiveness of consumer country governance and policy pathways, levers and innovations for transformative change in agrifood systems and trade with high biodiversity outcomes and equity. It explores the diverse actors in the governance system from the international, consumer side of telecoupled agrifood systems at actors of change, including stakeholders such as policy makers at the international, regional (e.g. European Union), and national levels; the private sector, the social movements and civil society involved in international biodiversity and equity governance initiatives on Transformative change pathways for biodiversity and equity. In doing so, the report serves as a first step in understanding agrifood system governance and transformation pathways, which will continue under diverse WPs. The report present desk research findings pertaining to four domains, namely: international governance & policy initiatives, EU Laws, policies and regulations, market & private sector mechanisms and initiatives, social movements and Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs). Specific emphasis will be placed on the different definitions that organisations use when they mention biodiversity and equity.

¹ We include the United Kingdom's current and future food environments - due to the partnership with the UK based NRI University of Greenwich in the TC4BE project.

1.2 Approach

As the report essentially provides an overview of real-world initiatives from these domains, it will not provide a theoretical overview. As a theoretical basis, the report follows key theories and concepts that underlie the project as whole, most importantly transformative change, telecoupling, food systems, and governance (see project's conceptual paper by Nelson et al. [2023]). This theoretical framework allows to identify the actors and institutions involved in the governance arrangements that could play as agents of change, such as the transnational actors (e.g. corporations and business associations; activist groups; scientific researchers and associations); the rules and norms that the different institutions embody; and the different ways in which actors interact and the formal and informal rules and norms that influence domestic policies. Doing so the focus of the analysis is on the agency each actor has on governance processes.

With regard to our approach to biodiversity and equity, we use the definitions of IPBES (Diaz et al., 2015). A growing body of literature has called for the pluralization of values and expansion of biodiversity towards more holistic and ontologically just conceptualizations (Howitt and Suchet-Pearson, 2006; Leventon et al., 2021; Pascual et al., 2021). Also in this project, biodiversity is acknowledged in its pluralism, that is, as a concept of instrumental, relational and intrinsic values. In the IPBES glossary **biological diversity** is defined as: *“The variability among living organisms from all sources including terrestrial, marine and other aquatic ecosystems and the ecological complexes of which they are a part. This includes variation in genetic, phenotypic, phylogenetic, and functional attributes, as well as changes in abundance and distribution over time and space within and among species, biological communities and ecosystems”* (Diaz et al., 2015).

The concept of **equity**², in the context of this project, is a comparative concept which examines i) the distribution of benefits and costs among peoples (distributive equity) ii) the procedures (procedural equity) and iii) the pre-existing conditions (contextual equity) that limit or facilitate people's access to decision-making procedures, resources and, thereby, benefits. Adapted from McDermott and Mahanty (2013)'s framework and the IPBES glossary (IPBES glossary), equity comprises three interlinked dimensions, namely **distributive equity** (the need to consider not just the allocation of benefits, but also of costs and risks), **procedural equity** (fairness in political processes and participation in decision-making), and **contextual equity** (recognises that the playing field is never level, but that people's capabilities and their access to resources and power determine the extent to which they are able to utilise procedural equity to determine the best distributive outcome for themselves). For specific definitions of the concepts refer to the [project glossary](#).

1.3 Structure of the report

The remainder of this report is structured as follows. In chapter 2 we provide a brief methodology used in this report. In the next chapters we subsequently discuss the international governance and policy initiatives (chapter 3), relevant EU policies, laws and regulations (chapter 4), private sector initiatives (chapter 5), and the initiatives from civil society and NGOs (chapter 6). Then how the diverse governance pathways are conceived in the terms of biodiversity and equity is presented in chapter 7, followed by a brief conclusion.

² In this document, the words 'equitable' and 'just' are used often throughout the document. The 'outer' layers of equity according to McDermott and Mahanty (2013) are loosely drawn and barely present.

2. Methodology

Drawing on an inventory of stakeholders in the TC4BE project conducted by the project partners (M2, M4, M5, M6), we identified and characterised the key stakeholders related to each governance pathway. We then conducted desk research (document analysis) to provide information relevant for the transition pathways, the different arrangements, and levers (such as strategies, policies, and initiatives).

Some of the key documents that reviewed and analysed in this document are presented in the **Table 2**. We analysed how the different stakeholders define and describe the concepts of “biodiversity” and “equity”. We have tried to capture the relevant information on the selected organisations in the report and we cross-checked sources to the best of our abilities. Any errors remain of course our own.

Table 2 Key documents analysed

Governance pathway	Stakeholder	Document(s)
International	CBD	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First Draft of The Post-2020 Global Biodiversity Framework (CBD, 2021). • Glossary For The First Draft of The Post-2020 Global Biodiversity Framework (CBD, 2022).
	UNDP	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • UNDP’s Food & Agricultural Commodity Systems Strategy 2020-2030 (UNDP, 2020).
	UNSFS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Towards a Common Understanding of Sustainable Food Systems (SFS, 2020).
	IPBES	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Global assessment report on biodiversity and ecosystem services of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES, 2019).
	IPCC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sixth Assessment (IPCC, 2023).
	FAO	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The State of the World’s Biodiversity for Food and Agriculture (FAO, 2019). • Strategic Framework 2022-2031 (FAO, 2021).
	IFAD	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strategy on Diversity, Equity and Inclusion (IFAD, 2021) • Strategy on Biodiversity 2022-2025 (IFAD, 2022).
	ILO	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Global Wage Report 2012/13: Wages and equitable growth (ILO, 2021).
	WTO	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Climate Change Adaptation and Trade. Policy brief. (WTO, 2022) • World Trade Report 2023. Re-globalization for a secure, inclusive and sustainable future (WTO, 2023).
European Union	EU Green Deal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • COM/2019/640 final: Communication From the Commission to the European Parliament, The Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions: The European Green Deal (European Commission, 2019)
	EU Farm to Fork Strategy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communication From the Commission to the European Parliament, The Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions: A Farm to Fork Strategy for a fair, healthy and environmentally-friendly food system. (European Commission, 2020b)
	EU Biodiversity Strategy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • COM/2020/380 final: Communication From the Commission to the European Parliament, The Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions: EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 (European Commission, 2020a)

Governance pathway	Stakeholder	Document(s)
	CAP	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regulation (EU) 2021/2116. • Regulation (EU) 2021/2115. • Regulation (EU) 2021/2117. • Approved Strategic Plans 2023 (European Commission, 2023).
Markets and Private sector	Fairtrade International	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fairtrade Mission. • Statement (Fairtrade, 2023).
	GCP	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Coffee Sustainability reference code (GCP, 2020).
	IDH	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public good Impact (IDH, 2020). • Landscape approaches (IDH, 2021). • Gender Toolkit (IDH, n.d.).
	POIG	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Verification Indicators (POIG, 2019).
	Rainforest Alliance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integrated Community Forest Management Position Paper (Rainforest Alliance, 2021a).
	RSPO	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Code of Conduct (2018a). • System Report (RSPO, 2018b). • Smallholder support fund (RSPO, 2022).
	Unilever	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regenerative agriculture principles with implementation guides (2021).
NGOs and Social Movements	ASEED	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Annual Report (ASEED, 2023) • Intersectionality Statement (2023).
	Friends of the Earth	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Replanting Agricultural Biodiversity in the CBC (FoE, 2022).
	GRAIN	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Highlights of our activities (GRAIN, 2022).
	Green Peace	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GreenPeace International Annual Report 2022 (Greenpeace, 2023b).
	La Via Campesina	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • La Via Campesina Annual Report (LVC, 2023).
	EnvonlVert	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Progress Report (EnvonlVert, 2022).
	Slow Food Europe	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discovering the Role of Food Environments for Sustainable Food Systems (Slowfood, 2021). • Manifesto (Slowfood, No date). • Position Paper (Slow Food, 20223).
	WWF	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Farming with Biodiversity (WWF, 2021). • Living Planet Report 2022 (WWF, 2022).

3. International governance and policy agreements

This chapter maps out and compares four different international governance initiatives in place at time of study (December, 2023). The cases focus on matters of biodiversity and are carried out by intergovernmental bodies. First, the approach to biodiversity and equity in the UN Sustainable Development Goals are analysed given their global and multidisciplinary reach. Section 5.3. looks at the OECD's stance on biodiversity and equity. Following, other UN supported initiatives are presented in section 5.4. Table 3 describes the Goals of each instrument, as well as their definitions of biodiversity and equity whenever present.

3.1. UN Sustainable Development Goals

The UN SDGs are a Plan of Action from the UN Department of Economic and Social Affairs, pledged by member states in 2015. The SDGs are a list of 17 goals, themselves further defined into sub-categories with smaller targets. The agenda is a multi-stakeholder international plan of action for people, planet, and prosperity. It also seeks to strengthen universal peace in larger freedom”.

The 17 goals cover a plethora of human rights issues, which are at the heart of the action plan. The justification for addressing biodiversity loss and climate change is inextricably linked to human rights issues: *“Natural resource depletion and adverse impacts of environmental degradation, including desertification, drought, land degradation, freshwater scarcity and loss of biodiversity, add to and exacerbate the list of challenges which humanity faces”* (UN General Assembly, 2015, p. 5). Moreover, when stating their reasons for pledging to protect nature, the Action Plan reads: *“We recognise that social and economic development depends on the sustainable management of our planet’s natural resources. We are therefore determined to conserve and sustainably use oceans and seas, freshwater resources, as well as forests, mountains and drylands and to protect biodiversity, ecosystems, and wildlife.”* (UN General Assembly, 2015, p. 9). The rationale for biodiversity having a place in this agenda is the contributions it has to human lives (i.e. an anthropocentric perspective). Table 3 summarises the Goals and subgoals that reflect biodiversity values in the **SDGs Plan of Action**. A unique definition of both **biodiversity** and **equity** is absent from this document, with the former borrowing the 1992 CBD definition, and the latter left undefined and up to Member States to draw up.

Table 3 SDGs and targets relevant to biodiversity conservation, equity & sustainable agrifood systems

SDGs	Targets	Related concepts
SDG 2. End hunger, achieve food security and improved nutrition, and promote sustainable agriculture	<p>2.2 By 2030, end all forms of malnutrition, including achieving, by 2025, the internationally agreed targets on stunting and wasting in children under 5 years of age, and address the nutritional needs of adolescent girls, pregnant and lactating women and older persons</p> <p>2.3. By 2030, double the agricultural productivity and incomes of small-scale food producers, in particular women, indigenous peoples, family farmers, pastoralists and fishers, including through secure and equal access to land, other productive resources and inputs, knowledge, financial services, markets and opportunities for value addition and non-farm employment</p> <p>2.4 By 2030, ensure sustainable food production systems and implement resilient agricultural practices that increase productivity and production, that help maintain ecosystems, that strengthen capacity for adaptation to climate change, extreme weather, drought, flooding, and other disasters and that progressively improve land and soil quality</p> <p>2.5 By 2020, maintain the genetic diversity of seeds, cultivated plants and farmed and domesticated animals and their related wild species, including through soundly managed and diversified seed and plant banks at the national, regional and</p>	Biodiversity Equity Transformation

SDGs	Targets	Related concepts
	international levels, and promote access to and fair and equitable sharing of benefits arising from the utilisation of genetic resources and associated traditional knowledge, as internationally agreed	
SDG 5: Gender equality and women's empowerment	<p>5.5. Ensure women's full and effective participation and equal opportunities for leadership at all levels of decision-making in political, economic and public life.</p> <p>5.5.a. Undertake reforms to give women equal rights to economic resources, as well as access to ownership and control over land and other forms of property, financial services, inheritance and natural resources, in accordance with national laws.</p> <p>5.5.b. Enhance the use of enabling technology, in particular information and communications technology, to promote the empowerment of women.</p> <p>5.5.c. Adopt and strengthen sound policies and enforceable legislation for the promotion of gender equality and the empowerment of all women and girls at all levels.</p>	Biodiversity Equity Transformation
SDG 10: Reduce inequality within and among countries	<p>10.1 By 2030, progressively achieve and sustain income growth of the bottom 40 percent of the population at a rate higher than the national average</p> <p>10.2 By 2030, empower and promote the social, economic and political inclusion of all, irrespective of age, sex, disability, race, ethnicity, origin, religion or economic or other status</p> <p>10.3 Ensure equal opportunity and reduce inequalities of outcome, including by eliminating discriminatory laws, policies and practices and promoting appropriate legislation, policies and action in this regard</p> <p>10.4 Adopt policies, especially fiscal, wage and social protection policies, and progressively achieve greater equality</p> <p>10.5 Improve the regulation and monitoring of global financial markets and institutions and strengthen the implementation of such regulations</p> <p>10.6 Ensure enhanced representation and voice for developing countries in decision-making in global international economic and financial institutions in order to deliver more effective, credible, accountable and legitimate institutions</p> <p>10.7 Facilitate orderly, safe, regular and responsible migration and mobility of people, including through the implementation of planned and well-managed migration policies</p>	Biodiversity Equity Transformation
SDG 12. Ensure sustainable production and consumption patterns.	<p>12.2. By 2030, achieve the sustainable management and efficient use of natural resources.</p> <p>12.3. By 2030, halve per capita global food waste at the retail and consumer levels and reduce food losses along production and supply chains, including post-harvest losses..</p> <p>12.6. Encourage companies, especially large and transnational companies, to adopt sustainable practices and to integrate sustainability information into their reporting cycle.</p>	Biodiversity Equity Transformation

SDGs	Targets	Related concepts
	<p>12.7. Promote public procurement practices that are sustainable, in accordance with national policies and priorities.</p> <p>12.8. By 2030, ensure that people everywhere have the relevant information and awareness for sustainable development and lifestyles in harmony with nature.</p> <p>12.c. Rationalize inefficient fossil-fuel subsidies that encourage wasteful consumption by removing market distortions, in accordance with national circumstances, including by restructuring taxation and phasing out those harmful subsidies, where they exist, to reflect their environmental impacts, taking fully into account the specific needs and conditions of developing countries and minimizing the possible adverse impacts on their development in a manner that protects the poor and the affected communities</p>	
SDG 13. Take urgent action to combat climate change and its impact	<p>13.1 Strengthen resilience and adaptive capacity to climate-related hazards and natural disasters in all countries.</p> <p>13.2 Integrate climate change measures into national policies, strategies and planning.</p> <p>13.3 Improve education, awareness-raising and human and institutional capacity on climate change mitigation, adaptation, impact reduction and early warning.</p> <p>13.b. Promote mechanisms for raising capacity for effective climate change-related planning and management in least developed countries and small island developing States, including focusing on women, youth and local and marginalized communities.</p>	Biodiversity Equity Transformation
SDG 14. Conserve and sustainably use the oceans, seas and marine resources for sustainable development	<p>14.a Increase scientific knowledge, develop research capacity and transfer marine technology, taking into account the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission Criteria and Guidelines on the Transfer of Marine Technology, in order to improve ocean health and to enhance the contribution of marine biodiversity to the development of developing countries, in particular small island developing States and least developed countries.</p> <p>14.c Enhance the conservation and sustainable use of oceans and their resources by implementing international law as reflected in United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea, which provides the legal framework for the conservation and sustainable use of oceans and their resources, as recalled in paragraph 158 of "The future we want"</p>	Biodiversity Equity Transformation
SDG 15. Protect, restore and promote sustainable use of terrestrial ecosystems, sustainably manage forests, combat desertification, and halt and reverse	<p>15.1 By 2020, ensure the conservation, restoration and sustainable use of terrestrial and inland freshwater ecosystems and their services, in particular forests, wetlands, mountains and drylands, in line with obligations under international agreements.</p> <p>15.2 By 2020, promote the implementation of sustainable management of all types of forests, halt deforestation, restore degraded forests and substantially increase afforestation and reforestation globally.</p>	Biodiversity Equity Transformation

SDGs	Targets	Related concepts
land degradation and halt biodiversity loss	<p>15.3 By 2030, combat desertification, restore degraded land and soil, including land affected by desertification, drought and floods, and strive to achieve a land degradation-neutral world.</p> <p>15.4 By 2030, ensure the conservation of mountain ecosystems, including their biodiversity, in order to enhance their capacity to provide benefits that are essential for sustainable development.</p> <p>15.5 Take urgent and significant action to reduce the degradation of natural habitats, halt the loss of biodiversity and, by 2020, protect and prevent the extinction of threatened species.</p> <p>15.6 Promote fair and equitable sharing of the benefits arising from the utilisation of genetic resources and promote appropriate access to such resources, as internationally agreed.</p> <p>15.7 Take urgent action to end poaching and trafficking of protected species of flora and fauna and address both demand and supply of illegal wildlife products.</p> <p>15.8 By 2020, introduce measures to prevent the introduction and significantly reduce the impact of invasive alien species on land and water ecosystems and control or eradicate the priority species.</p> <p>15.9 By 2020, integrate ecosystem and biodiversity values into national and local planning, development processes, poverty reduction strategies and accounts.</p>	
SDG 17. Strengthen the means of implementation and revitalize the Global Partnership for Sustainable Development	17.10 Promote a universal, rules-based, open, non-discriminatory and equitable multilateral trading system under the World Trade Organization, including through the conclusion of negotiations under its Doha Development Agenda.	Biodiversity Equity Transformation

Equity is one of the key concepts of all the SDGs. However, some of them are directly related to equity among women/men, developed/developing countries as it is shown in Table X such as SDG 2, SDG 5, and SDG 10. Other SDGs are directly related with food systems transformations such as SDG 2, SDG 12, SDG 13, SDG 14 and SDG15.

In response to the SDGs, and regarding **SDG 8**, the UN-adjacent International Labour Organization (ILO) produced an analysis of the advances and shortcomings of this goal. SDG8 on Decent Work and Economic Growth aims to “*Promote sustained, inclusive and sustainable economic growth, full and productive employment and decent work for all.*” As the ILO states, SDG 8 aims to integrate the economic, social, and environmental dimensions of sustainable development. To achieve inclusive and sustainable economic growth for full employment and decent work, ILO states that an integrated process is needed in order to drive balanced progress across these three dimensions. Although in the **SDG Plan of Action** the environmental facet of SDG8 is weakly stated, the document has few mentions of ‘**sustainability**’ (which itself is never defined), the ILO takes into consideration this gap and establishes the urgent need for policymakers to emphasise the need to include the social dimensions and merge them with the economic aspects of SDG8. Moreover, ILO has stated that decoupling of economic growth and the destruction of nature is not progressing fast enough, leading to a clear trend whereby global economies are growing at the expense of biodiversity and ecosystems (ILO, 2023). Other scholars have made similar sceptic claims towards decoupling for biodiversity protection (Parrique et al., 2019; Hickel & Kallis, 2020).

3.2. United Nations initiatives

The following section presents relevant instruments developed by the UN covering food production, biodiversity conservation and equity. Table 4 summarises the selected public policies and structures the contents of this section.

Table 4 United Nations instruments and documents promoting agrifood system transformation

Institution	Section	Goals	Document analysed
FAO	3.2.1	To abolish hunger and ensure food safety	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strategic Framework • Biodiversity Mainstreaming Platform Biodiversity Report
UN Sustainable Food Systems Program	3.2.2	To ensure sustainability in agrifood systems.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Report on the Conference of the One Planet (10YFP) • Sustainable Food Systems (SFS) Programme
IFAD	3.2.3.	Financial institution for the sustainable development of rural areas.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strategy on Biodiversity 2022-2025 • Strategy on Diversity, Equity and Inclusion

3.2.1. FAO's Strategic Framework

The Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) is a UN organism specialised in efforts to abolish hunger internationally through food security endeavours. Relevant to this project are both the 2019 **FAO Biodiversity report**, which provides “a global assessment of biodiversity for food and agriculture” in relation to the UN Commission on Genetic Resources for Food and Agriculture, as well as the FAO 2022-2031 Strategic Framework. The former document establishes definitions and understandings of **biodiversity**, whereas the framework gives way into establishing the extent to which the FAO addresses biodiversity among its other objectives.

The Biodiversity Report (FAO, 2019) borrows its **biodiversity** definition from the CBD (1992), in line with other UN organisms, and describes “*biodiversity for food and agriculture*” as “*the biological diversity that is needed to sustain food and agriculture production. It encompasses all the components of biological diversity that make up agricultural ecosystems. These components include the variety and variability of animals, plants and microorganisms. This biodiversity, which exists within species among species and among ecosystems, is necessary to sustain the key functions, the structure and the processes of agricultural ecosystems.*”. In this definition, **biodiversity** is conceptualised as a means to an end, a necessary component of food safety, rather than an intrinsic good.

In FAO's strategic plan, **biodiversity** makes few appearances. Firstly, the plan sets “*Four betters*” goals, where they pledge to improve three aspects of food safety: better production, better nutrition, better life and better environment. It is the later pillar which aims to “*Protect, restore and promote sustainable use of terrestrial and marine ecosystems and combat climate change (reduce, reuse, recycle, residual management) through more efficient, inclusive, resilient and sustainable agri-food systems.*” This goal is itself made up of three aspects: 1) Climate change mitigating and adapted agri-food systems, 2) Bioeconomy for sustainable food and agriculture and 3) Biodiversity and ecosystem services for food and agriculture. In this third point, the outcome statement is “Biodiversity for food and agriculture maintained and sustainable use, conservation and restoration of marine, terrestrial and freshwater ecosystems, and their services promoted through adoption of targeted policies and practices” (FAO, 2021, p. 17).

FAO hopes to achieve these goals by investing in **innovative technologies** and approaches which can intensify production with lesser environmental impact, highlighting the impact that a fourth industrial revolution can have on this sector. They argue technology “*creates an unprecedented opportunity to move towards and agriculture sector that produces more with less, needing less water, land and energy, saving biodiversity and reducing carbon emissions.*” (FAO, 2021, p. 19).

Equity is not formally defined in either of the documents studied here, however its principles play a significant role in **FAO's objectives and goals**. As above-mentioned, the **FAO Biodiversity report** follows from the Commission on Genetic Resources for Food and Agriculture, whose *"main objective [...] is to ensure the sustainable use and conservation of biodiversity for food and agriculture and the fair and equitable sharing of benefits derived from its use, for present and future generations."* This mission statement features both the notion of equity and the concept of intergenerational equity. Distributive equity, however, is only concerned with the distribution benefits, not ills, of agricultural practices. In the biodiversity report, non-western knowledge systems are notably present in defining concepts. For instance, in describing pollination, it is said that *"Scientific studies, citizen-science projects and indigenous and local knowledge all help to build up understanding of the economic, environmental and sociocultural values of pollination [...]"* (FAO, 2019, p. 130).

Compared to biodiversity, **equity** is much more present in the **FAO Strategic Framework**. As described previously, the document sets four 'betters', notably for equity is that of "Promot[ing] inclusive economic growth by reducing inequalities (urban/rural areas, rich/poor countries, men/women" (FAO 2021, p.17-18). The goal itself is made of seven points, described in Table 5.

Table 5 FAO's strategy on 'Better Lives' in the agrifood system, adapted from FAO (2021)

Goal	Outcome Statement
1. Gender equality and rural women's empowerment	Women's equal rights, access to, and control over resources, services, technologies, institutions, economic opportunities, and decision-making ensured, and discriminatory laws and practices eliminated, through gender-responsive policies, strategies, programmes, and legal frameworks
2. Inclusive rural transformation	Inclusive rural transformation and revitalization of rural areas ensuring equal participation of, and benefits to poor, vulnerable and marginalised groups accelerated through implementation of targeted policies, strategies, and programmes
3. Achieving sustainable urban food systems	More efficient, inclusive, resilient, and sustainable urban and peri urban agri-food systems transformation that addresses urban poverty, food insecurity and malnutrition, enables healthy diets and catalyses inclusive and sustainable rural transformation, promoted through the adoption of supportive policies and programmes, and the initiation and scaling-up of actions and investments by national and local stakeholders
4. Agriculture and food emergencies	Countries facing, or at risk of acute food insecurity provided with urgent livelihood and nutrition assistance and, adopting a humanitarian-development nexus and its contribution to peace approach, their populations equipped with appropriate capacities to better withstand and manage future shocks and risks
5. Resilient agri-food systems	Resilience of agri-food systems and livelihoods to socio-economic and environmental shocks and stresses strengthened through improved multi-risk understanding and effective governance mechanisms for implementation of vulnerability reduction measures
6. Hand-in-Hand (HIH) Initiative	Agricultural transformation and sustainable rural development accelerated through targeting the poorest and the hungry, differentiating territories and strategies, and bringing together all relevant dimensions of agri-food systems through analysis and partnerships.
7. Scaling up investment	Transformation towards sustainable agri-food systems with large scale impacts on reducing inequalities and eradicating poverty and hunger accelerated through increased public and private investment, and improved capacities to leverage future investments.

Most relevant for **equity** are **goals 1, 2 and 5**, which establish the targets of equity and describe a redistribution based on needs, putting the marginalised and poor at the forefront of these goals. FAO prioritises **'triggers of change'** towards greater **equity through income wealth redistribution**, stating that *"Improving food security and nutrition is difficult if income and wealth distribution are not improved. For instance, billions of people cannot afford nutritious diets, while global wealth accumulates in small fractions of the population. Reducing cross- and within-country inequalities may also positively impact on geo-political instability."* (FAO, 2021, p. 10-11).

3.2.2. UN Sustainable Food Systems Programme Sustainable Food Systems (SFS) Programme

The SFS programme is a **multi-stakeholder programme** launched in 2015 by the UN, comprising government agencies, civil society organisations, research and technical institutions, international organisations, and private sector entities with the goal of promoting sustainability in agrifood systems. During the **4th SFS conference in Hanoi, Vietnam**, an outcome document for **transformation** was drafted. The objectives of this conference, and by extension of the document, was to *"- Take stock of progress since the 1st Global Conference of the SFS Programme in 2017 in South-Africa, taking into account its conclusions and identified areas for future work; - Identify new food systems challenges; - Offer a dialogue platform to share experiences, exchange ideas, propose concrete and innovative initiatives, and highlight relevant tools, approaches and good practices; - Showcase concrete opportunities for responsible public and private investments in sustainable food systems, as a contribution towards the SDGs; - Stimulate specific high-level commitments and pledges from governments, other food system stakeholders and resource partners."*

The document expresses the urgency for **food systems to engage with issues of biodiversity loss**, calling back to the Post-2020 Biodiversity framework. However, this was not without **putting people at the forefront**: *"People need to be put at the centre of food systems transformation by including a focus on ensuring decent incomes, protecting human rights and providing nutritious and affordable food, while addressing climate change and biodiversity loss."* (One Planet, 2023). The lack of formal definitions, target-setting or dialogue about biodiversity loss indicates this issue remains low on the agenda for FSF stakeholders.

The One Planet definition of Sustainable Food systems reads as follows; *"A sustainable food systems approach considers food systems in their totality, considering the interconnections and trade-offs among the different elements of food systems, as well as their diverse actors, activities, drivers, and outcomes. It seeks to simultaneously maximise societal outcomes across environmental, social (incl. health) and economic dimensions."* (One Planet, 2020, p. 58). *Nonetheless, in the 2023 conference, the environmental aspects of sustainability have been neglected and an integral half of the definition forgotten. Moreover, there is no present discussion nor definition of equity that could be found in the FSF available documents. However, there is a pledge to create solutions "adapted to specific national contexts, with more innovation needed in terms of technologies that are customised to smallholders and the poor, while overcoming gender inequalities".* (One Planet, 2023, p. 5)

3.2.3 IFAD Strategy on Biodiversity 2022-2025 and Strategy on Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion

The International Fund for Agricultural Development (IFAD) is a UN agency which operates as a financial institution for the sustainable development of rural areas. Here, we discuss its **Biodiversity and Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion strategies**.

The **IFAD biodiversity framework** aims to better integrate biodiversity into its operations. IFAD borrows from CBD (1992) on their definition of **biodiversity**, with particular emphasis on **diversity in agriculture**, which they note as a *"key element in building resilience for rural families and their livelihoods. Biodiversity at every level (genetic, species and ecosystem) is a foundational pillar for life-sustaining ecosystem services leading to multiple benefits. They include long-term productivity, climate change adaptation and mitigation, food security and improved nutrition."* (IFAD, 2022). From this extract, it is established that **biodiversity** is framed in terms of its contribution to people. It follows that IFAD's indicators for good biodiversity practices do not aim to quantify biodiversity in

any ecological measurements, but rather explore the ratio of finance instruments, policy dialogues and partnerships they engage in for the 2021-2025 period. Issues of effectiveness, sustainability, and impact of said initiatives are uncounted for. Moreover, no targets are set for percentages or budgets for biodiversity.

The term '**equitable**' is present six times along the strategy document, and defined in the **IFAD Strategy on Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion** as *"giving people what they need to make things fair. Equity achieves fairness by treating people equally or differently, depending on their needs."* Thus, following the multidimensional framework for assessing **equity**, this definition falls under the needs-based allocation of **distributive equity**. This allocation is based on their diversity parameters of gender, geographical representation, and disability. Unlike biodiversity, equity is measured using **Key Performance Indicators (KIP)** (IFAD, 2022).

3.3. World Trade Organization (WTO)

The World Trade Organization (WTO) is the global international organisation which sets rules of trade between nations (WTO, 2023). Seeing the impact global trade has on climate change and biodiversity loss, its influence must be accounted for. The link between global trade and Climate Change is explicitly admitted by the **WTO's Climate Change Adaptation and Trade Policy Brief (WTO, 2022)**, however **biodiversity** is not mentioned in said policy. **Equity** is just as silent. In this document, Climate Change is seen as a phenomenon which is deeply affecting global trends in trading and as such must be taken into account (WTO, 2022).

Looking at the **World Trade Report of 2023**, the annual WTO publication on the state of affairs of trends in trade, trade policy issues and multilateral trading systems, it seems that the WTO offers no definitions of **biodiversity**, despite mentioning it several times. The report also acknowledges biodiversity at the side of the harmful impacts economic growth has on nature; *"economic growth and material progress are also placing unsustainable strains on the global environment, resulting in rising levels of greenhouse gas emissions, rapid biodiversity loss, the over-exploitation of natural resources and the spread of air, land and water pollution"* (WTO, 2023, p. 19). However, they also acknowledge trade can contribute to improving environmental sustainability, and in this report, they are offered a series of measures to do so, such as decarbonization of maritime and aviation transport, stricter environmental policies and improving efficiency and (green) technology. (WTO, 2023). Moreover, WTO advocates for *"Re-globalization – or an increase in international cooperation and integration"* Since *"[it] is likely to result in environmental dividends because it encourages inherently greener trade, for example by means of digitally delivered services, and because it allows for more integrated trade and environmental governance."* (WTO, 2023, p.89).

In the **World Trade Report of 2023**, it is also argued that re-globalization can reduce **poverty and inequality**, yet it must be based *"on principles of fairness and equity, with human development at the core"* (WTO, 2023, p. 107). A definition of equity is not given in this document either, but terms such as *'inclusive'* and *'inequality'* are widely used. For instance, women are acknowledged to be underrepresented in economies, and the historical and contextual causes as to why are discussed. Moreover, the historical, **unequal distribution of benefits across the value chain workers** is mentioned, as well as the **emerging inequalities from global trade** which favour developed nations over developing economies (Goldberg and Larson, 2023; ILO, 2012; Karabarounis and Neiman, 2013; Abdih and Danninger, 2017; Elsby, Hobijn and Sahin, 2013). On the reporting nature of this document, no targets or future pathways of action to address these issues (be it reparations or ways forward) are established.

3.4. CBD Post-Global Biodiversity Framework

The Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) is a legal instrument of the United Nations for **biodiversity conservation**, currently aiming to develop a **Post-2020 action framework**. This framework has been in development for years, with a final product yet to be agreed upon. The fifth Working Group meeting on the Post-2020 Global Biodiversity Framework took place at the Kunming-Montreal Conference of the Parties (COP) 15 in December 2022, where a series of recommendations were adopted (UNCBD, 2022). Here the goal of the framework was described as *"to catalyse, enable and galvanise urgent and transformative action by Governments, subnational and local governments, and with the involvement of all of society to [halt and reverse]/[address*

the trend of] biodiversity loss, to achieve the outcomes it sets out in its vision, mission, goals and targets, and thereby to contribute to the three objectives of the Convention on Biological Diversity, and to its Protocols. The purpose is [to implement]/[the full implementation of] the three objectives of the Convention [in a balanced manner.]". The three objectives of the CBD in question are:

- a) The conservation of biological diversity,
- b) The sustainable use of the components of biological diversity and
- c) The fair and equitable sharing of the benefits arising out of the utilisation of genetic resources.

Notably, **equity** plays a role in the description of this last goal. **Equity** is part of the **CBD theory of change framework**, which "*acknowledges the need for appropriate recognition of gender equality, women's empowerment, youth, gender-responsive approaches and the full and effective participation of indigenous peoples and local communities in the implementation of this framework.*" (CBD,2021). **Intergenerational equity** was moreover explicitly mentioned in the framework (CBD, 2021). Following **McDermott and Mahanty's framework (2013)**, it could be argued the outer layers of equity are rather loosely defined, with the quote above establishing the target of equity (who), yet the goal of equity (why) goes unmentioned, and parameters are not set.

The theory of change framework states that **equity** will be implemented through a **rights-based approach**, closely drafting the how of equity in the **CBD Post-2020 framework**. Following, the core contents of equity (distributive, procedural and contextual) are likewise absent. Despite citing the IPBES Global Biodiversity Report as a blueprint for this framework, the **CBD Post-2020** draft so far seems to trail behind in its equity goals, with scholars calling for a greater acknowledgement of Indigenous Peoples and Local Communities (IPLCs) in the document (Friedman et al., 2022). Moreover, the OECD has criticised the Post-2020 draft for lacking ambition in its approach to biodiversity conservation, particularly in regard to Target 18 which aims to "*Redirect, repurpose, reform or eliminate incentives harmful for biodiversity, in a just and equitable way, reducing them by at least US\$ 500 billion per year, including all of the most harmful subsidies, and ensure that incentives, including public and private economic and regulatory incentives, are either positive or neutral for biodiversity.*" (UN CBD, 2021). The OECD claims that placing the focus merely on reducing harm and failing to mention incentives to promote and scale-up biodiversity is a missed opportunity, one that allows for passivity and lacklustre results (Karousakis, 2022).

3.5. IPBES Global Assessment Report on Biodiversity. United Nations

The Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES) is an international initiative of experts set to provide science-based policy recommendations for an environmentally viable future. **The 2019 Assessment report** is a thorough document based on over 15,000 scientific publications on the current state of **biodiversity** globally. The goal of this document is to "*provide governments, the private sector and civil society with scientifically credible and independent up-to-date assessments of available knowledge for better evidence-informed policy decisions and action at the local, national, regional and global levels*" (IPBES, 2019). It is a clear and accessible document which has no legal power but undoubtedly influences policy at all levels on biodiversity conservation.

Biodiversity is defined by IPBES in relation to '**nature**', which was defined in scientific terms as well as in the context of other knowledge systems, leaving way for indigenous ontologies and what they deem "*nature's contributions to people*"; which range from material, intrinsic, spiritual or recreational.

3.6. IPCC Sixth Assessment

The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) is an intergovernmental and transdisciplinary body of the UN for assessing scientific evidence related to Climate Change (CC). The IPCC Sixth Assessment Report was published in March 2023 during the 58th Panel Session in Interlaken, Switzerland. Acknowledging the interconnected natures of climate change, agrifood systems and biodiversity, this report is highly relevant for the TC4BE project. The Report asserts that "Climate resilient development strategies that treat climate, ecosystems and biodiversity, and human society as parts of an integrated system are the most effective" (IPCC, 2023, p. 84). The panel

adopts the same definition of biodiversity as that of the CBD, IPCC and UN. In the 2023 report they note adaptation to CC has occurred in the past decade across sectors and regions. The experts define adaptation actions for biodiversity and ecosystem services as “responses like minimising additional stresses or disturbances, reducing fragmentation, increasing natural habitat extent, connectivity and heterogeneity, and protecting small-scale refugia where microclimate conditions can allow species to persist” (IPCC, 2023, p. 22). Moreover, they now have extremely high confidence that adaptation can generate “multiple additional benefits such as improving agricultural productivity, innovation, health and well-being, food security, livelihood, and biodiversity conservation as well as reduction of risks and damages” (IPCC, 2023, p.22). The report suggests the need for better mitigation and adaptation measures moving forward to safeguard biodiversity and food safety, whilst also warning that every warming increment in global temperature, risks will become “increasingly complex and difficult to manage”, often leading to irreversible changes such as species extinction and worsened human health and wellbeing (IPCC, 2023).

3.7. Summary

This chapter presented the series of international policies and strategies which are related to **food systems** and that might play a prominent role in promoting food systems transformations for **biodiversity** and **equity**. These stakeholders and institutions are: the UN Sustainable Development Goals, three UN institutions and programmes (FAO, UNSFS, IFAD), the WHO, the CBD, IPBES and IPCC.

Out of the instruments highlighted in this section, the **UN SDGs** have had the greatest reach regarding **biodiversity** and **equity**, albeit not without criticisms from the academic community (Lashitew, 2021; Covic et al., 2021). From the analysis of the definitions of biodiversity and equity, it was concluded that both terms are present in the documents that were reviewed to a large extent. Moreover, most of these documents place human well-being at the forefront of the **UN SDGs**. Finally, in relation to the **SDGs sub-targets**, one of the most prominent findings is that most of the targets presented have as an aim to overcome **biodiversity loss** and **social inequalities**.

Overall, there is a gap in the **SDGs** on promoting biodiversity and equity in food systems, as these objectives are disconnected from the international agenda. The only SDGs that promote equity and biodiversity on food systems are SDG 2 and SDG 12. For enhancing **food systems transformations** more coordinated actions, goals and milestones among the diverse SDGs are needed.

Regarding the definition of **biodiversity**, **FAO**, **UNSFS** and **IFAD** all make use of the 1992 CBD definition of biodiversity (Table 6). This is a scientific definition provided by academia, which focuses on biological systems and processes. One of the main differences with the CBD conceptualization of biodiversity, is that **UNSFS** contextualises the importance of biodiversity by mentioning the essential role it plays in sustaining (human) life, highlighting the instrumental value of biodiversity for wellbeing.

Regarding **equity**, there exists much more variation in definitions and the extent to which this concept is included in the documents reviewed: **FAO** does not mention this term in any of the reviewed documents (FAO 2019a, FAO 2019b and FAO 2021). **IFAD** defines **equity** in relation to distributive justice yet fails to acknowledge the contextual and procedural aspects of equity (McDermott and Mahanty, 2023). **USFS** centres people’s wellbeing across their definitions of sustainability but does not define equity although they do mention the need to pay special attention to historically marginalised groups. In contrast, **WTO** offers no definitions for biodiversity and equity in its climate change adaptation or sustainable futures plans. The **CBD Post-2020** framework introduces equity to the discussion of biodiversity with its ‘theory of change’, which recognizes the need for greater equality for marginalised and underrepresented groups such as women and young people. Its equity framing follows from McDermott and Mahanty (2013)’s definition of intergenerational equity.

The **IPBES** latest reports (from 2019 and 2023, respectively) and **IPCC** offer the most differing takes on **biodiversity** and **equity** from this governance pathway. Both, IPBES and IPCC, pose an understanding of nature and biodiversity which includes humans and co-evolves with culture, unlike the dualistic division among humans and nature which prevails in other instruments. Their definitions successfully acknowledge the plural values of biodiversity (instrumental, relational and intrinsic) set by Leventon et al. (2021) . Following, **equity** is understood as inextricably linked with

climate justice. This merged framework of socio ecological values and challenges has been suggested to be at the core of transformations in biodiversity conservation (Pascual et al., 2021). Notably, the IPBES report is the only instrument in this group to make explicit mention of indigenous peoples and non-Western modes of knowledge production.

Table 6 Definitions of Biodiversity and Equity in the Actor Group International Policy

Report	Definitions - Biodiversity	Definitions - Equity
UN SDGs	"Biological diversity" means the variability among living organisms from all sources including, inter alia, terrestrial, marine and other aquatic ecosystems and the ecological complexes of which they are part: this includes diversity within species, between species and of ecosystems.	--
CBD-UN-- United Nations Convention on Biological Diversity -Post-2020 Global Biodiversity Framework (Draft)		"The theory of change for the framework acknowledges the need for appropriate recognition of gender equality, women's empowerment, youth, gender-responsive approaches and the full and effective participation of indigenous peoples and local communities in the implementation of this framework. Further, it is built upon the recognition that its implementation will be done in partnership among organisations at the global, national and local levels to leverage ways to build a momentum for success. It will be implemented taking a rights-based approach and recognizing the principle of intergenerational equity"
IFAD-- Strategy on Biodiversity 2022-2025 and Strategy on Diversity, Equity and Inclusion		"Equity is about giving people what they need in order to make things fair. Equity achieves fairness by treating people equally or differently, depending on their needs."
UN Sustainable Food Systems Programme -- 2nd Global Conference of the One Planet (10YFP) Sustainable Food Systems (SFS) Programme		"[There is] more innovation needed in terms of technologies that are customised to smallholders and the poor, while overcoming gender inequalities". (One Planet, 2023, p. 5)
ILO		"The need for a fair distribution of the burdens and benefits arising from transformative change to be shared by all, with changes required across the value systems, norms, institutions, technologies, production structures and consumption behaviour of societies." Social justice also requires societies to take responsibility for the well-being of future generations. Social justice between generations is intrinsic to sustainability, which is defined as "meeting the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs" (United Nations 1987)."
FAO -- Biodiversity Mainstreaming Platform Biodiversity Report // Strategic Framework	Biological diversity is the variability that exists among all living organisms on land, in fresh water bodies and in the oceans. It also includes the ecological complexes in which these organisms interact. Biological diversity encompasses the diversity within species, the diversity between species and the diversity of ecosystems. Biodiversity for food and agriculture is the biological diversity that is needed to sustain food and agriculture production. It encompasses all the components of biological diversity that make up agricultural ecosystems. These components include the variety and variability of animals, plants and microorganisms. This biodiversity, which exists within species among species and among ecosystems, is necessary to sustain the key functions, the structure and the processes of agricultural ecosystems.	--

Report	Definitions - Biodiversity	Definitions - Equity
IPCC -- Synthesis Report Of the IPCC Sixth Assessment Report (AR6)	Biodiversity or biological diversity means the variability among living organisms from all sources including, among other things, terrestrial, marine and other aquatic ecosystems, and the ecological complexes of which they are part; this includes diversity within species, between species and of ecosystems	The principle of being fair and impartial, and a basis for understanding how the impacts and responses to climate change, including costs and benefits, are distributed in and by society in more or less equal ways. Often aligned with ideas of equality, fairness and justice and applied with respect to equity in the responsibility for, and distribution of, climate impacts and policies across society, generations, and gender, and in the sense of who participates and controls the processes of decision-making.
IPBES- Global Assessment Report	<i>"Nature, in the context of the Platform, refers to the natural world, with an emphasis on biodiversity. Within the context of science, it includes categories such as biodiversity, ecosystems, ecosystem functioning, evolution, the biosphere, humankind's shared evolutionary heritage, and biocultural diversity. Within the context of other knowledge systems, it includes categories such as Mother Earth and systems of life. Other components of nature, such as deep aquifers, mineral and fossil reserves, and wind, solar, geothermal and wave power, are not the focus of the Platform. Nature contributes to societies through the provision of contributions to people."</i>	<i>"Promoting inclusive governance approaches through stakeholder engagement and the inclusion of indigenous peoples and local communities to ensure equity and participation"</i>
WTO	N/A	N/A

4. European Union policies, laws and regulations related to agri-food systems

The policies regulating telecoupled agrifood systems in the **European Union** are the **European Green Deal**, which encompasses the **Farm to Fork Strategy (F2F)**, the **Biodiversity Strategy**; and the **CAP**. They all have been implemented in the EU since 2020 and were enforced in 2023. The aim of this chapter is to describe how the diverse strategies, policies, laws, norms, and regulations in the European Union are related to food systems and food systems transformations towards biodiversity and equity.

4.1. European Green Deal

The European Green Deal is a transformative roadmap set forth by the European Union to guide the region towards a sustainable, climate-neutral economy. This comprehensive initiative, introduced in December 2019, encompasses a broad range of policy measures and legislative proposals aimed at reducing greenhouse gas emissions, promoting energy efficiency, and fostering a circular economy. At its core, the Green Deal targets climate neutrality by 2050, with ambitions to strengthen the EU's global leadership in environmental conservation.

Key components of the Green Deal include the European Climate Law, which legally binds the 2050 climate neutrality objective, setting specific policies to reach this objective. Moreover, the Deal emphasises increasing the EU's emission reduction target to at least 55% by 2030, prioritising the advancement of renewable energy sources and energy efficiency measures. It also places significant emphasis on the modernization of the EU's energy system, for example, promoting sustainable agriculture, and fostering a just and inclusive transition through the Just Transition Mechanism.

To promote systemic transformations towards climate neutrality the Green Deal includes strategies for mobilising financial resources to support sustainable projects and initiatives, as well as a strong focus on international cooperation to advance global efforts in combating climate change. Additionally, it carries a strong social dimension, aiming to ensure that the transition is fair and inclusive, with provisions to support communities and workers most affected by the shift towards a green economy. Overall, the European Green Deal sets a comprehensive framework, guiding the EU's efforts to mitigate climate change, promote sustainability, and position itself as a leader in global environmental action. As part of the Green Deal, the Farm to Fork (F2F) strategy, the Biodiversity Strategy and the CAP were developed to align sectoral objectives such as food systems, biodiversity and agriculture to reach climate neutrality by 2050.

4.2. The Farm to Fork Strategy (F2F)

In 2020, the EU unveiled the F2F aim to foster sustainability in the EU agricultural systems (European Commission, 2020). To achieve this objective, this Strategy outlines several goals for archiving sustainability transformations. Some of these are the increase in food security and resilience, a reversal of biodiversity loss, and actions to handle diverse types of crises, particularly the economic ones. Particularly, the goal for ensuring food security is raised in relation to a "food supply that is "safe, nutritious, affordable and sustainable" ensuring that this supply could be maintained during the crisis (European Commission, p.12). This policy does not include specific targets for the reduction of greenhouse emissions from food systems or the externalised impacts. Moreover, the F2F strategy aims "to reduce the environmental and climate footprint of the EU system and strengthen its resilience, ensuring food security in the face of climate change and biodiversity loss and lead a global transition towards competitive sustainability from farm to fork and tapping into new opportunities" (European Commission, 2020, p. 7). The strategies for coping with this strategy are:

"Ensuring that the food chain, covering food production, transport, distribution, marketing and consumption, has a neutral or positive environmental impact, preserving and restoring the land, freshwater and sea-based resources on which the food system depends; helping to mitigate climate change and adapting to its impacts; protecting land, soil, water, air, plant and animal health and welfare; and reversing the loss of biodiversity; · ensuring food security, nutrition and

public health – making sure that everyone has access to sufficient, nutritious, sustainable food that upholds high standards of safety and quality, plant health, and animal health and welfare, while meeting dietary needs and food preferences; and · preserving the affordability of food, while generating fairer economic returns in the supply chain, so that ultimately the most sustainable food also becomes the most affordable, fostering the competitiveness of the EU supply sector, promoting fair trade, creating new business opportunities, while ensuring integrity of the single market and occupational health and safety” (European Commission, 2020, p.8).

Moreover, the F2F Strategy, “will support the global transition to sustainable agri-food systems, in line with the objectives of this strategy and the SDGs. Through its external policies, including international cooperation and trade policy, the EU will pursue the development of Green Alliances on sustainable food systems with all its partners in bilateral, regional and multilateral fora” (European Commission, 2020, p.8). To achieve this, the EU will collaborate with other regions and countries, to “enable the development of comprehensive, integrated responses benefiting people, nature and economic growth” (European Commission, 2020, p.18).

According to the F2F Strategy, the trade policy will be used to support and be part of the EU transition (European Commission, 2020, p.18), and will try to implement this vision on all the EU bilateral trade agreements, such as the EU Chief Trade Enforcement Officer. Some of the areas where this policy will be implemented are on the commitments from third countries regarding the animal welfare, the use of pesticides and the antimicrobial resistance of crops. For this, the EU strives to promote international standards in the relevant international bodies and encourage the production of agri-food products under high safety and sustainability standards. Moreover, the F2F is willing to support small-scale farmers to meet these standards and access to markets.

“The EU will focus its international cooperation on food research and innovation, with particular reference to climate change adaptation and mitigation; agro-ecology; sustainable landscape management and land governance; conservation and sustainable use of biodiversity; inclusive and fair value chains; nutrition and healthy diets; prevention of and response to food crises, particularly in fragile contexts; resilience and risk preparedness; integrated pest management; plant and animal health and welfare, and food safety standards, antimicrobial resistance as well as sustainability of its coordinated humanitarian and development interventions. The EU will build on ongoing initiatives and integrate policy coherence for sustainable development in all its policies. These actions will reduce the pressure on biodiversity worldwide. As such, better protection of natural ecosystems, coupled with efforts to reduce wildlife trade and consumption, will help to prevent and build up resilience to possible future diseases and pandemics. To reduce the EU’s contribution to global deforestation and forest degradation, the Commission will present in 2021 a legislative proposal and other measures to avoid or minimise the placing of products associated with deforestation or forest degradation on the EU market.” (European Commission, 2020, p.8).

There exist four principal areas where these actions need to be implemented: 1) Food production food, 2) Food consumption, 3) Food processing and distribution, and 4) Food loss and waste. Regarding food production, some of the actions that need to be taken on consideration.

This policy aims that food systems should function within planetary limits and that the impacts of food chains should be neutral or positive. Some of the objectives that this policy aims are to reduce the land designated to agriculture (10%), the use of fertilisers (20%), the use of pesticides (50%), and antimicrobials (50%). Moreover, the land under organic farming should be increased by 25%.

In relation to food consumption, there are some actions included by the F2F strategy, aiming to reduce deforestation linked to the consumption of some products that are produced outside Europe, but that are causing deforestation in the countries and regions where they are produced. Particularly, linked to the F2F strategy, in 2023, the EU Regulation (EU) No 1169/2011(FIC Regulation), related to the information that is provided to consumers, entered in force the 13th of December of 2014. One of the main objectives of the regulation is to provide nutritional information on the labels, an action that is enforced since 13 December 2016. This regulation standardised the labelling requirements for online and distance selling or buying in a shop. It also clarifies that food business operators are responsible for providing this information. As part of the F2F Strategy, the European Commission revised the EU rules on the information provided to consumers. The aim of this action

is to ensure better labelling information to help consumers make healthier and more sustainable food choices and tackle food waste. Some of the actions proposed are:

- To introduce harmonised mandatory front-of-pack nutrition labelling and set nutrient profiling criteria to restrict claims made on foods
- To extend mandatory origin or provenance information for certain products.
- To revise the rules on date marking ('use by' and 'best before' dates).

Moreover, the F2F Strategy, is proposing a sustainability labelling framework to empower to make informed and sustainable food choices. This initiative aims to provide a label with the information related to the sustainability of food products. In addition to other labelling that are already being implemented, such as the pack nutrition labelling, the animal welfare labelling and the "green claims", this labelling strategy will cover the information that consumers have in relation with the nutritional, climate, environmental and social aspects of food products. The proposal for these initiatives is already under review by the EU Commission. Related to the Food processing and distribution, the F2f strategy aims to "ensuring that the food chain, covering food production, transport, distribution, marketing and consumption, has a neutral or positive environmental impact, preserving and restoring the land, freshwater and sea-based resources on which the food system depends; helping to mitigate climate change and adapting to its impacts; protecting land, soil, water, air, plant and animal health and welfare; and reversing the loss of biodiversity" (Farm to Fork Strategy, p.4)

Despite this major step in looking towards an integrated food system in the policy, the mechanisms for achieving these goals are not yet established by the European Commission (2020). When analysing the policy targets for 2030, these two strategies, and particularly the F2F strategy, focus on the agricultural sector and how to transform its practices towards the conservation of biodiversity. Moreover, it has a strong component in food security and human health, without representing major shifts in the Food industry (Schebesta & Candel, 2020).

As a result of the F2F strategy, the EU has engaged in dialogues with producer countries in order to address steps towards sustainable food systems beyond European borders. For instance, in September 2022 the dialogue on sustainable food systems between the EU and Colombia, Ecuador and Peru took place aiming to promote a constructive exchange of ideas to find common grounds and initiatives that can pave the way for further collaborations to push food systems towards sustainability " (EU, 2022). These dialogues included representatives of the EU, Ministries, members of the private sector and representatives of public and academic institutions from Colombia, Peru and Ecuador. Workshops and discussions to create a pluri-visual understanding and joint strategies for sustainable food systems took place over the two-day event. (EU, 2022). No concrete plans or ratified documents have to date been published as a result of these dialogues.

4.3. Biodiversity Strategy for 2030

The EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 is a comprehensive plan aimed to address the ongoing process of biodiversity crisis. This strategy was introduced in May 2020.

Some of the key components of the strategy include the protection of at least 30% of the EU's land and sea areas, as well as the restoration of degraded ecosystems. It also seeks to integrate biodiversity considerations into decision-making processes across various sectors, such as agriculture, forestry, fisheries, and urban planning. Emphasising the intrinsic value of biodiversity, the strategy, in all of the actions, proposes to use nature-based solutions to address societal challenges, such as climate change, pollution, and natural disasters.

The strategy prioritises the implementation of strict protection measures for species and habitats, alongside efforts to combat invasive alien species and reduce the pressures on biodiversity caused by pollution and overexploitation. The strategy also highlights the importance of engaging citizens, stakeholders, and businesses in the conservation and sustainable use of biodiversity, promoting education and awareness as important tools for achieving its objectives.

Furthermore, the strategy touches upon global initiatives, seeking to boost international cooperation and partnerships to address biodiversity loss beyond the EU's borders, recognizing that biodiversity conservation is a global concern.

4.4. European Union's new Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) (2023-27).

In December 2021, the EU issued the New Common Agricultural Practice (CAP) for all member states in the period of 2023 until 2027. This regulation is a reform of the CAP, which had last been revised in the year 2013, and which outlines the challenges, goals and orientations for the future of agriculture in Europe. This policy aims to “foster a smart, competitive, resilient and diversified agricultural sector ensuring long-term food security; to support and strengthen environmental protection, including biodiversity, and climate action and to contribute to achieving the environmental and climate-related objectives of the Union, including its commitments under the Paris Agreement; to strengthen the socio-economic fabric of rural areas” (European Council, 2023). The stated objectives for the CAP are a) making the CAP more result-driven and market-oriented, 2) Boosting modernization & Boosting sustainability 3) Including economic, social, environmental and climate sustainability of the agricultural, forestry and rural areas and 4) helping reduce the Union legislation-related administrative burden for beneficiaries (European Council, 2022). The policy is comprised of three regulations with differing focus:

- Regulation (EU) 2021/2116, repealing Regulation (EU) 1306/2013 on the financing, management and monitoring of the CAP;
- Regulation (EU) 2021/2115, establishing rules on support for national CAP strategic plans, and repealing Regulations (EU) 1305/2013 and 1307/2013;
- Regulation (EU) 2021/2117, amending Regulation (EU) 1308/2013 on the common organisation of the agricultural markets;

Regulation 2021/2115 in turn mandates all 28 Member States to develop a CAP Strategic Plan in accordance with their national context, which were drafted and presented to the EU by the end of the year 2022. The CAP is strictly concerned with setting standards, financial incentives and penalties only within the EU.

Historically, the CAP has advocated for the intensification of agriculture in the EEA, and thus has been a key driver in “the loss of wild and domesticated agro-biodiversity in the European Union in the last 50 years” (Simoncini et al., 2019). However, this latest reform aims to tackle biodiversity loss more effectively than previous attempts; the CSPs of each Member States set out goals for climate, natural resources and biodiversity separately. This is done despite their interlinked nature, however, the division ensures more specific target-setting and attention paid to each component. Member State's CSPs are moreover legally obligated to show more climate ambition than previous reforms to avoid ‘backsliding’ of environmental and climate contributions.

The regulation claims to have strengthened compliance standards for good agriculture and environmental conditions (GAECs), in accordance to the standards set out in the “Commission communication on the ‘Future of Food and Farming’ and the MFF for the years 2021 to 2027, established by Council Regulation (EU, Euratom) 2020/2093” (Article 41, Regulation 2021/2115) as well as in cohesion to the Nature Directives set out in Natura 2000 and Priority Action Frameworks (PAF) of Member States (Article 75, Regulation 2021/2115). The CAP has dedicated a Specific Objective entirely to biodiversity, under a mixture of mandatory and voluntary instruments, as part of their “new green architecture”;

- Under GAEC 9, Natura 2000 grasslands are permanently protected and designated environmentally sensitive, protecting 9 million hectares in Europe.
- An additional 1.9 million hectares of agricultural and forest land fall under Natura 2000 compensation payments to enhance biodiversity.
- At the national level, voluntary eco-schemes and agri-environment climate interventions.
- Under the Agri-environmental climate commitments (AECC), voluntary interventions are set out by member states in ecosystem restoration, coexistence projects, protection of farmland dependent species and regimes from grazing and mowing grasslands, peatlands and wetlands.

Strengthening of environmental ambitions is reflected in requirements such as the conservation of carbon ecosystems (such as wetlands and peatlands) and support of management practices for carbon storage and reducing emissions, catch-crops and agroforestry. Conservation of pollinators and soil diversity are discussed as key areas of focus for ecological sustainability. This “new green architecture” reflects on the financial instruments of the CAP in the form of increased financial aid

for small-scale farmers and an increased budget for direct payments for eco-schemes, based on a result-driven (rather than the previous action-oriented) measure. These eco-schemes are a new instrument aimed at supporting environment and climate resilient farmland practices which previously received no financial aid. According to the EC report, “Some eco-schemes will support practices that were obligatory under the past ‘greening’ requirements or that are included in new GAEC standards, but on a more ambitious scale – for example, funding of crop rotations more ambitious than those required under GAEC 7, or areas beneficial for biodiversity beyond those required by GAEC 8.” (European Commission, 2023, p. 66). A study carried out with opinions from over 300 experts on agricultural policy by Pe’er et al. (2022) cautions these eco-schemes could seriously water down environmental ambitions if this instrument is used for funding already-existing practices that could fall under Conditionality instruments and argue that eco-schemes must remain highly ambitious to avoid this potential pitfall. However, some authors have stated that on the short-term nature of the eco-schemes, which will be implemented on an annual basis, whereas most effective conservation measures can often require many years to come into fruition; there is a danger that eco-schemes will in turn prioritise short-term, less effective projects (Pe’er et al., 2022).

Moreover, there exists scholarly concern over the fragmented implementation of biodiversity conservation in the CAP reform; Explicit mention of ecological connectivity issues is made whereby farmers are made to comply to the maintenance of (at least) 3% of their arable land intact, and are encouraged to pursue agroforestry practices and other alternative methods which will be monitored by Member States in the pursuit of achieving the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 target of high diversity landscape features in 10% of the EU agricultural land (European Commission, 2023). Crops neighbouring high biodiversity areas are indirectly addressed under the EU Integrated Pest Management (IPM), which is part of the GAEC framework and thus a condition for compliance. However, these measures fail to take on a landscape-scale conservation that includes either collective action or spatial planning measures (Falco, 2022; Pe’er et al., 2022). Some hope that the flexibility of eco-schemes might bridge that gap and “make farmed systems less hostile and better-connected environments thereby increasing the chances for successful spatial adjustment of geographic ranges in the light of climate change” (Adam et al., 2022).

In addition to the heightened ecological conditions, the CAP has introduced a social conditionality, a framework for the improvement of the social aspects of the agricultural policy focused on the social and labour rights of farm workers. The CAP mandates farmers “must provide their workers with a written description of their agreed working conditions and must ensure a safe and healthy working environment. If farmers breach these rules their CAP payments will be reduced.” (European Commission, 2023, p. 16). Member states must decide on enforcement methods in compliance with national labour and social systems (Article 46, Regulation 2021/2115).

The CAP has long been concerned with ensuring the viability of agriculture in Europe, and this latest resolution particularly focuses on small farmers and their specific challenges, in response to previous backlash on barrier entries and challenges for small-scale rural producers (Simoncini et al, 2019; Volkov et al., 2019; Dwyer, 2014). The CAP reform will reduce basic payments for big farms in favour of almost tripling the allocated budget for complementary payments for small farmers. Approximately, a total of 29 billion euros will be given annually to “address the persistent gap between agricultural income and the average wage in the whole economy as well as the disparities in income between agricultural sectors and farms” (European Commission, 2022). Moreover, particular care is placed in the budget allocation for support for young and new farmers (Article 57, Regulation 2021/2115). In accordance with EU values, Article 33 of the CAP states that “There should therefore be a particular focus on promoting the participation of women in the socio-economic development of rural areas, with special attention to farming, supporting women’s key role.” (Regulation 2021/2115). Gender equality within the CAP implementation is regulated by Member States; 12 Member States refer to involvement of women whereas 11 refer to young people in decision making bodies (European Commission, 2022).

4.3. European Union Trade Agreements

4.3.1 EU-Colombia-Peru-Ecuador Trade Agreement

The EU-Colombia-Peru-Ecuador Trade Agreement is one of the several bilateral trade agreements between the European Union and non-EEA nations that aim to propel free trade among the parties. It was signed in 2012, under the decision 2012/735/EU. Originally, this decision included only Colombia and Peru, but it was revised in 2016 to incorporate neighbouring Ecuador with decision 2016/2369(EU, 2023). This agreement “aims to open markets on both sides and improve the stability of the trade relationship between the partners. It provides for progressive and reciprocal liberalisation by means of an ambitious and balanced free trade area.” (EU, 2023). The agreement came at a crossroads for the EU’s trade policy, right before the seventh Environmental Action Plan (7th EAP) was approved and goals to incorporate international environmental challenges were ratified in 2013 (McNeill, 2020). Image X illustrates where the Colombia-Peru agreement falls within the temporal landscape of EU international trade policy in the context of environmental policy, based on McNeill (2020).

Colombia, a country of interest for TCforBE, is where the EU invests most of its international funds in the agricultural, fuel and mining sectors (EU, 2023). This agreement sets out human rights and sustainable development essential elements. It dedicates Title VII, Chapter 2 to the ‘protection of biodiversity and traditional knowledge’, and advocates for the ‘sustainable use’ of biological diversity. (EU, 2012). As McNeill (2020) notes, terms such as ‘environment’ and ‘sustainable use’ are amply present but loosely defined across FTAs. Equity is moreover addressed in this agreement in the context of genetic diversity of seeds, whereby these shall be “*In accordance with Article 15 paragraph 7 of the CBD, the Parties reaffirm their obligation to take measures with the aim of sharing in a fair and equitable way the benefits arising from the utilisation of genetic resources.*” (EU, 2021,p. 64). Following, equity is mentioned on Article 275 related to Climate Change, stating that “The Parties are resolved to enhance their efforts regarding climate change, which are led by developed countries, including through the promotion of domestic policies and suitable international initiatives to mitigate and to adapt to climate change, on the basis of equity and in accordance with their common but differentiated responsibilities and respective capabilities and their social and economic conditions, and taking particularly into account the needs, circumstances, and high vulnerability to the adverse effects of climate change of those Parties which are developing countries” (EU, 2012, p. 82).

Figure 2 Timeline of EU's strategies for establishing EPAs, based on McNeill (2020)

Shown in green are the agreements discussed in this section. The resolutions in black mark internal EU agreements and reports which mark a significant shift in the EU's approach to trade agreements; from interim agreements in the early 2000s to increasingly bilateral and environmentally concerned texts nowadays.

4.3.2. EU- EAC Regulations & EU-Kenya Economic Partnership Agreement

In 2014, a coalition of East African countries (Burundi, Kenya, Rwanda, Tanzania and Uganda) and the EU negotiated an Economic Partnership Agreement for trade in goods and development cooperation. The partnership concerns imports from and exports from the East African Community (EAC) to the EU, with the former being dominated by coffee, flowers, tea, tobacco, fish and vegetables and the latter concerning machinery and mechanical appliances, equipment parts and medical products (European Union, 2023a). Said working document includes "protection of environment and biodiversity in particular" among its rights and obligations (European Commission, 2019a, p. 20). Moreover, it places further stress on sustainable fisheries, where sustainability is understood to "account economic, environmental and social impacts". (European Commission, 2019a, p.24). Kenya was the only country to ratify the EU-EAC agreement, and as such it could not be applied. Following this, In 2016, Kenya and the EU began further negotiations for a EU-Kenya trade agreement that "move[s] forward under 'variable geometry' [...] to advance on the bilateral implementation of the EU-EAC EPA, with the addition of trade and sustainable development provisions." (European Commission, 2023a). Negotiations for this partnership agreement were last published in June 2023, but it is yet to be finalised or ratified after its fourth round. Notable to this paper is the explicit mention of Trade & sustainable development in the document, the specificities of which are not yet publicly available (European Commission, 2023b)

4.3.3. EU- Central Africa EPA agreement

In 2009, Cameroon and the EU co-signed an interim EPA, which is seen by the involved parties as a temporary solution to be eventually replaced with a fully-fledged EPA with Central African region's nations, including Gabon, Sao Tome and Principe, The Central African Republic, Equatorial Guinea, Chad, Congo and the Democratic Republic of the Congo (European Commission, 2023c). These nations make up a significant portion of the EU's imports of wood, cocoa and tropical fruits. The interim EPA aims to a) help reduce poverty, b) promote regional integration, economic cooperation and good governance in Central Africa, c) increase Central Africa's production, export and supply capacities, d) improve Central Africa's ability to attract foreign investment and lastly, e) increase its capacities in terms of trade policy and other trade-related issues (European Commission, 2021). Although this EPA sets food security goals that directly tackle agrifood systems, there is no mention of environmental sustainability, biodiversity conservation to date. However, in the working document the parties acknowledge the importance of sustainable development and thus "agree to ensure that sustainability considerations are reflected in all titles of the EPA and to draft specific chapters covering environmental and social issues." (European Commission, p. 33, 2019b).

4.4. Summary

In this chapter, three main European initiatives were reviewed; the **EU Green New Deal**, comprising the **Farm to Fork Strategy**, the **Net Zero Deforestation commitment** and the **Biodiversity Strategy for 2030**, the new **CAP** and, the **trade Agreements between the EEA and producer countries of Colombia, Kenya and Cameroon**.

In general, these policies and strategies are part of the new **EU's roadmap to transformation**, the **EU Green New Deal**. The **EU Green Deal** has an aim to reach climate neutrality in the EU's economy by 2050. Here we illustrate how the EU addresses sustainability in the food sector, halting deforestation, protecting biodiversity and achieving food security through the **F2F**, **Net Zero Deforestation Biodiversity strategy and CAP** respectively. Although these fall under the Green New Deal umbrella, biodiversity and equity these issues are encompassed through largely separate and independent resolutions. The new **CAP** brings about a new structure and approach to financing agriculture in the EU and abroad the EU borders. This new strategy aims to scale up the different strategies to other regions and countries, supporting small-scale farmers and making more ambitious biodiversity conservation goals. On the other hand, the **F2F Strategy** is the first strategy at the EU level aiming to regulate diverse food systems activities, from production to consumption, looking at agrifood systems from a systems perspective. Some of the law initiatives related to the **F2F Strategy** are still under review, but will need to have a deeper analysis on their impacts on biodiversity and equity.

In these policies, definitions of **biodiversity** orbit around the **EU Biodiversity Strategy**, which all other documents cite back to. In this strategy, the EU makes strides towards a more holistic understanding of biodiversity that goes beyond the scientific-instrumental definition found in international policies such as the CBD and opts instead for a definition much more similar to the IPBES. The **EU Biodiversity Strategy** definition of biodiversity includes instrumental and relational values of nature (See Table X). However, in practice, the **CAP** and **F2F Strategies** seem to only focus on the instrumental value of biodiversity, showcasing the EU's struggles to meaningfully transform practices to reflect new values. Discussions on biodiversity were all but missing in the reviewed **trade agreements**, with the exception of the **EU-Colombia-Peru-Ecuador** which mentions genetic seed diversity.

In terms of **equity**, a key finding relates to the new **CAP** and its new-found focus on smallholders, women and young farmers. Moreover, there is an expressed interest to address all steps of the agrifood value chain, evolving the previous perspective which mainly focused on producers and consumers and largely ignoring intermediaries. As part of this perspective shift, the **EU Green Deal** expresses the need to work alongside producer countries via bilateral agreements. These EU-level policies have implications on biodiversity and equity in agrifood systems beyond the European borders. It is stated in the **F2F strategy** and implied in the **Net Zero Deforestation Regulation** that trading of agrifood and timber products with producer countries will be affected, yet **EU trade agreements** presented in section 4.3. are not yet suited to address these new commitments.

Despite the diverse **policies, strategies, laws and regulations** that are being implemented or are being developed at the **EU level**, in this section it is found that the components of **biodiversity and equity** in food systems need to be strengthened, for them to secure the reduction of the impacts on equity and biodiversity of agrifood chains at different levels.

Table 7 Definitions of Biodiversity and Equity by diverse stakeholders in the European Union governance pathway

Report	Definitions - Biodiversity	Definitions - Equity
EU Green Deal	Not defined. In relation to ecosystem services. Mentioned in the context of 'biodiversity loss'	N/A
EU Farm to Fork Strategy	N/A	Mentioned once, but undefined: "The European Green Deal is an opportunity to reconcile our food system with the needs of the planet and to respond positively to Europeans' aspirations for healthy, equitable and environmentally friendly food"
EU Biodiversity Strategy	"From the world's great rainforests to small parks and gardens, from the blue whale to microscopic fungi, biodiversity is the extraordinary variety of life on Earth. We humans are part of, and fully dependent on, this web of life: it gives us the food we eat, filters the water we drink, and supplies the air we breathe. Nature is as important for our mental and physical wellbeing as it is for our society's ability to cope with global change, health threats and disasters. We need nature in our lives. "	In relation to seeds genetic diversity.
New Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) 2023-2027	Refers to the EU Biodiversity Strategy, addresses biodiversity in farmlands more specifically.	N/A
EU-Colombia-Peru-Ecuador Trade Agreement	"The Parties furthermore reaffirm their sovereign rights over their natural resources and recognise their rights and obligations as established by the CBD with respect to access to genetic resources, and to the fair and equitable sharing of benefits arising out of the utilisation of these genetic resources."	N/A
EU-Kenya Economic Partnership Agreement	N/A	N/A
EU- Central Africa EPA agreement	N/A	N/A

5. Private sector initiatives and market mechanisms

In the European market, several private sector policies, initiatives and actions towards **biodiversity** and **equity** have been implemented. Promoting biodiversity and equity in the market space often requires private sector initiatives, that in turn build on specific market mechanisms. This section intends to identify these initiatives (including the underlying market mechanisms). Next, some examples are laid out as case studies for the study of the discursive practices at play in the market and private sector in the discussions of biodiversity and equity.

5.1. Private sector initiatives

Biodiversity Bonds. Bonds have been used to finance activities that address climate change and environmental issues, such as biodiversity and equity, providing a means to increase green investments. In the EU, they constituted a mere 0.6% of all bonds in 2014, surging to 8.9% by 2022. This growth mirrors the financial sector's interest in sustainable products and investors' demand for eco-friendly projects. Green bonds issued by diverse entities, like governments, corporations, supranational, and subnational bodies, help also private (niche) companies as they animate investing in sustainability issues, anticipating further expansion due to the European Green Deal's ambitious environmental and climate objectives (EEA, 2023). One expected benefactor of green bonds in the future is the NextGenerationEU recovery plan, aimed at young European farmers (EEA, 2023).

Payment for Ecosystem Services (PES). "Ecosystem services" encompass a wide range of natural benefits, including the provisioning of food, water, and timber, the regulation of air quality and climate, the provision of opportunities for recreation and education, and the essential functions of soil formation and nutrient cycling (Fripp, 2014). PES involves beneficiaries providing compensation to service providers in exchange for these services, typically through a series of payments in return for continuous benefits. The fundamental principle underlying PES is to ensure equitable compensation for service provision (Fripp, 2014). PES can be financed through three different types of payments (Fripp, 2014):

1. Public payment schemes through which the government pays land or resource managers to enhance ecosystem services on behalf of the wider public.
2. Private payment schemes, or self-organised private deals, in which beneficiaries of ecosystem services contract directly with service providers.
3. Public-private payment schemes that draw on both government and private funds to pay land or other resource managers for the delivery of ecosystem services.

PES aims therefore to directly connect actors in the food system, via direct payments, shortening the supply chain and supporting landowners to act more sustainable, e.g., increasing biodiversity and their own private equity.

European and national labelling and certification initiatives. In many high-income countries, particularly in Western Europe and Northern America, labels and certificates serve as the primary means of informing consumers about sustainability. These labels also play a crucial role in government policies aimed at enhancing sustainability in the marketplace (e.g, Ingenbleek et al., 2012; Clark et al., 2017). Traditionally, labels, often in the form of logos or symbols, are affixed to product packaging to signal compliance with established standards to consumers at the point of purchase (Gracia et al., 2011). By doing so, they are a fundamental part of the information that consumers consider when making buying decisions. However, recently, static labels have faced criticism for their limited impact on driving the behaviourist changes necessary to achieve the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) (Ingenbleek & Krampe, 2022) and increase more biodiversity and equity. Despite these criticisms and the call for more innovative, data-driven approaches, labels and certificates remain a prominent choice for private producing companies and retailers to convey information into consumer markets.

Certification Schemes. Whereas labels constitute the marks and logo's that are communicated to the consumers, certification schemes constitute the standards behind these logos. The standards

are the rules that producers or other actors in the value chain voluntarily comply with in order to get certified. With the certification, their products can carry the labels. The labels differentiate their products from those of competitors which, at least for some segment on the market, translates into willingness to pay higher prices. Examples are Fair Trade, Rainforest Alliance, and UTZ. Not all certification organizations use labels though, some don't communicate the standards to consumers but are used in business-to-business markets, as procurement standards for retailers for example. A prominent example is Global GAP which sets standards for food safety, quality as well as sustainability. For suppliers these standards act as a "license to deliver". Some specifically aim to improve the livelihoods of small-scale palm oil farmers like the Asian Agri' One to One Partnership Commitment (Asian Agri, 2023) or the RSPO Smallholder Support Fund (RSSF) (RSPO, 2022).

Brands. Brands are among the most valuable assets of a company. They are easily recognized by buyers and as such they play an essential role in routine-based purchases. Because their brands are of so much value, companies tend to protect their brands against negative publicity. Hence, certification schemes can help to prevent negative publicity on biodiversity and equity aspects. Otherwise, companies may compensate for their negative impact, for example through **Certified Sustainable Palm Oil Credits**: Companies purchase certified sustainable palm oil credits to offset the use of non-certified palm oil in their products, thereby supporting sustainability and equity initiatives.

Sustainable niche companies. Sustainable niche companies make a statement against the big brands. They show that sustainable production or trade are possible by setting standards that are substantially higher than those of their mainstream competitors. Prominent examples are Fair Trade and Organic companies (for example of Tony Chocolonely in the chocolate industry).

Pre-competitive platforms. Because sustainability is an issue that is of importance to all companies in a particular industry, they established organizations in which they discuss the commonalities. These are labelled pre-competitive because it is illegal for them to discuss issues that affect market competition (like price agreements). Examples of such organizations are SAI Platform and the Roundtable on Sustainable Palm Oil (RSPO).

(Premium) pricing initiatives have become a significant focus, with various approaches aimed at promoting fairness, sustainability, and transparency. One notable facet of this movement is the emphasis on price transparency initiatives, where companies strive to make the entire supply chain of their products more visible, ensuring that fair compensation is provided to farmers. True prices, as recently implemented by retailers and niche companies are examples of such initiatives (True Price, 2023; Tony's Chocolonely, 2023a).

Another avenue within pricing strategies involves offering premiums for quality and sustainability. Companies recognize and reward farmers for cultivating high-quality crops or adhering to sustainable farming practices, thus fostering biodiversity-friendly approaches. Nespresso's AAA Sustainable Quality™ Program, for instance, provides substantial premiums ranging from 30-40% to farmers who meet specific sustainability standards, promoting what is known as 'green coffee' (Nespresso, 2023). In a similar vein, Fairtrade introduces an extra Fairtrade premium pricing system, empowering producers to invest in projects of their choice (Fairtrade, 2023).

Information approaches. There exists a growing need for multi-stakeholder approaches to guide and advise the private sector on ways to make their businesses more sustainable. Benchmarking organisations like the World Benchmarking Alliance create transparency by showing what different companies in an industry contribute. Independent think tanks such as Questionmark (Questionmark, 2023) pioneer data-driven research for sustainable food systems, aiding the private sector to leverage sustainable change. Questionmark targets and connects actors across the food system ecosystem from governments and industries to civil society and scientists in Europe. Another example is that of The Sustainability Consortium (TSC), an organisation of many members from the private sector and scientists. TSC uses science-based approaches to improve the sustainability of supply chains through research-based tools, funds and other initiatives (TSC, 2023a)

These are some examples of market and private sector mechanisms and initiatives that promote biodiversity and equity in line cocoa, coffee, and palm oil value chains. They demonstrate the

importance of sustainable sourcing, ethical practices, and innovative business models in these industries to address environmental and social challenges.

5.2. Private sector cases

Following the marketing and private sector initiatives that were identified in the previous section, in this section we present seven case examples which exemplify each of the different initiatives. Moreover, we analyse the discourses these initiatives have regarding biodiversity and equity on the review of key documents.

These market initiatives comprise three **certification schemes** (Fairtrade International, Rainforest Alliance and RSPO); a **direct sourcing initiative** (IDH); **two business ecosystem initiatives** (POIG, GCP); two examples of **corporate initiatives** (De Drie Mollen coffee and Unilever); and three examples of **pricing strategies** (Tony Chocolonely- cocoa, Nespresso; LIDL and True Pricing).

5.2.1. Certification Schemes

Fairtrade International

Fair Trade International (Fairtrade, from now on) is a sustainability label co-owned by over 1.8 million farmers and workers. Its goal is to ensure fair wages and build food sovereignty. The Fairtrade website states: "Our mission is to connect disadvantaged producers and consumers, promote fairer trading conditions and empower producers to combat poverty, strengthen their position and take more control over their lives." (Fairtrade, 2023). The documents reviewed for this section were the Constitution of the Association and the Report on Fairtrade's policy on Sustainable Agriculture. As a farmer-focused market mechanism, it was found the Constitution of the Association placed much emphasis on equity, having it as its first tenet. Equity and transparency particularly are seen as the tools through which a fairer trade system for food producers can materialise (Fairtrade, 2022). The association describes equity as "recognizing the rights and responsibilities of all members towards furthering the objectives of the Association in relation to their capacity to do so.". Here, distributive equity (McDermott and Mahanty, 2013) is expressed on a capacity-based, considering both goods and ills, rights, and obligations. Moreover, the governance structure of Fairtrade, alongside its co-ownership, ensures the association veils for procedural equity in a way any international public policy is yet to incorporate. Equity is targeted, goal-oriented and carries through to the procedural agreements of the organisation, checking all the boxes theorised by McDermott and Mahanty (2013).

Biodiversity, on the other hand, is not defined in either document or mentioned only once in the Sustainable Agriculture report. In said document, they claim Fairtrade is betting on agroforestry since this agriculture technique is most aligned "with [our] mission, vision, and Theory of Change. It explicitly addresses core Fairtrade topics such as social justice, biodiversity, and empowering vulnerable or marginalised rural producers.". However, this alleged core topic is not explained further in the document.

Rainforest Alliance/UTZ

The Rainforest Alliance is an international non-profit which brings together business, agriculture and forests by employing social and market forces for forest protection and the empowerment of farmers and forest communities (Rainforest Alliance, 2023a). It counts with its own certification and labelling program for producers which comply with certain environmental and social sustainability standards. The 2021 "Integrated Community Forest Management Position Paper" outlines the non-profit's approach to "addressing forest degradation through integrated community forest management, including the principles that we believe must guide the global community's broader efforts" (Rainforest Alliance, 2021a). In this document, biodiversity is not defined, yet it is expressed as a tool through which ecosystem and social resilience is achieved. The position paper states; "Forest management activities that enhance biodiversity mean forests are less affected by pests, diseases, and fires, and recover more quickly. These diverse and more resilient forests in turn provide a wider array of products to local communities, increase soil stability, and regulate water cycles,

which further secure crop yields and livelihoods. Combined with strong and effective governance at community level, community forestry has proven to increase social, economic, and ecological resilience globally".

Since 2018, the certification program UTZ has merged with Rainforest Alliance, joining powers and expertise to "to create a better future for people and nature and to be an even better partner for the many stakeholders we work with" (Rainforest Alliance, 2023b). According to the Rainforest Alliance statement on UTZ, the now phased-out label "stands for more sustainable farming and better opportunities for farmers, their families, and our planet."

Roundtable On Sustainable Palm Oil (RSPO)

The RSPO is a voluntary instrument established in 2004 for stakeholders across the palm oil supply chain "to develop and implement global standards for sustainable palm oil" (RSPO, 2023). Stakeholders range from NGOs focused on social and/or environmental issues to producers and consumer goods manufacturers. It counts with a certification seal awarded to smallholder producers. Moreover, consumer goods manufacturers can purchase Certified Sustainable Palm Oil Credits from RSPO smallholders and thus include a RSPO label on packaging for products including non-RSPO palm oil. Multiple documents were consulted for establishing RSPO's discourses of biodiversity and equity. In a Monitoring & Evaluation system report from 2018, the most recent publicly available, the RSPO sets a goal to "[Protect] Biodiversity, or the variety of life, forms the foundation of the health of ecosystem services and allows for ecosystems to adjust to disturbances (resiliency). Conservation of biodiversity includes the preservation of rare, threatened, and endangered species, and preservation of HCV areas" (RSPO, 2018). The RSPO Biodiversity & High Conservation Values Working Group (BHCBWG), has set to identify biodiversity & ecosystem service metrics to monitor this goal since 2018, yet no standards have yet been published. As far as equity goes, the word was not found across the documents regarding Human Rights and Social Standards (HRSS). One recommendation to include gender quotas was found in the 2021 "Practical Guidance on Gender Inclusion" document (RSPO, 2021). Moreover, the organisation denounced the way in which many fail to understand the contextual reasons for gender inequality in the palm oil value chains. However, in documents regarding indigenous rights, working wages, child labour or gender inequality, social justice, equality, or equity were not described (RSPO 2021; RSPO 2018). No targets, standards or specific quotas were set by RSPO for either equity or biodiversity.

5.2.2. Direct Sourcing

IDH

The IDH (the Dutch Sustainable Trade Initiative) is an organisation supporting direct sourcing aiming to connect producers and buyers more directly, setting targets for environmental and social sustainability jointly in a contextual, landscape-specific level, though a 'covening' process. Due to this landscape approach, sustainability goals are set by the governance bodies of producers and buyers and standards are not set by IDH directly, making it more challenging to assess their approach to biodiversity or equity. In their 2016-2020 report, IDH celebrates their efforts in halting deforestation, noting: "IDH focuses on deforestation-vulnerable landscapes in Côte d'Ivoire, Ethiopia, Kenya, Liberia, Indonesia, and Brazil, across pulp and paper, palm oil, timber, soy, tea, and cocoa supply chains." (IDH, 2020). It seems IDH conceptualises biodiversity as a vulnerable entity to be protected from deforestation. In terms of equity, IDH has developed its own Gender Toolkit and a Gender Guide, both documents aimed to exemplify and explore good practices in the global supply chain to achieve greater gender equality. (IDH, n.d.) The toolkit particularly aims for Gender Transformative practices, which tackle the structural, systemic issues that cause inequality rather than focusing efforts on treating symptoms. (IDH, n.d.) Moreover, IDH has a Production, Protection and Inclusion approach (PPI) to landscape management, where the last pillar veils for the improvement of lives of farmers and forest-dependent communities "thereby reducing their incentives to encroach forests." (IDH, 2021).

5.2.3. Business ecosystem initiatives and NGOs

POIG

The Palm Oil Innovation Group (POIG) is a multi-stakeholder initiative of NGOs and progressive palm oil producers that “strives to achieve the adoption of responsible palm oil production practices by key players in the supply chain.” (POIG, 2023). Building upon the RSPO, POIG sets several verification indicators for producers, which ensures they comply with the initiative’s charter. Protecting ecosystems is seen by POIG as a responsibility the palm oil industry must address due to its history with deforestation. In this charter, biodiversity is addressed as ‘biodiversity conservation’, often alongside ‘carbon conservation’ (POIG, 2019). Producers are expected to comply with High Carbon Stock and High Conservation Values, as well as to protect and conserve wildlife by carrying out surveys, and present management plans for rare, endangered or threatened species, while addressing poaching and traditional hunting by local communities (POIG, 2019). These requirements convey an understanding of local contexts and interlinkages between social and environmental conservation, whereby equity and biodiversity are being tackled concomitantly by recognizing IPLC’s dependency on natural resources. Moreover, POIG describes several requirements which deal with equity, such as inequity in natural resource management (requirement 1.7: water accountability) and all sub-requirements of requirement 2, which addresses partnership with communities: IPCL sovereignty, food security, humane social conditions (highlighting women’s empowerment) and worker’s rights.

Global Coffee Platform

The Global Coffee Platform (GCP) is a business ecosystem initiative of producers, traders, roasters, governments and NGOs engaged in the coffee supply chain dedicated to making the coffee sector more sustainable. It strives towards a collaborative, holistic and aligned farmer-oriented agenda for coffee sustainability (GCP, 2023a). The Coffee Sustainability Reference Code provides a clear guideline for stakeholders of the coffee chain to “advance their coffee sustainability efforts, collaboratively and effectively” (GCP, 2023b). In this document, a set of goals and indicators are presented. Biodiversity is the sole focus of goal 8, which states “Producers protect and restore natural resources including biodiversity, soil and water, are better able to adapt to climate change and are remunerated for environmental services provided to society.” Here, biodiversity is described to include “protected and endangered native flora and fauna” as well as soil biota (GCP,2020). This is measured through the maintenance of a ‘balanced ecosystem’, particularly by protecting natural forests and ecosystems, pledging no deforestation or conversion since 2014. The reference code also covers the issues of equity extensively, with goals 1 and 7 targeted at improving equity along the coffee production chain. However, the term is not explicitly defined.

5.2.4. Informative Approaches

The Sustainability Consortium (TSC)

TSC is a global organisation whose goal is to transform supply chains by decoupling production from its impacts on people and the planet (TSC, 2023a). The organisation is comprised of “manufacturers, retailers, suppliers, service providers, NGOs, civil society organisations, governmental agencies and academics” (TSC, 2023a). It follows a science-based approach, with thousands of peer-reviewed studies under their organisation. In relation to food systems change, TSC partakes in a sustainable coffee project called “The Sustainable Coffee Challenge”, which aims to “make coffee the first sustainable agricultural product in the world” by creating a series of tools to help actors across the coffee value chain to improve their practices (TSC, 2023b). Moreover, TSC employs financial tools such as the Resilient Agriculture Accelerator Fund to “strategically scale voluntary regenerative conservation on farms in the U.S.” (TSC, 2023 c). TSC serves as an example of a multistakeholder organisation which brings actors from several sectors together to jointly tackle sustainability challenges in the private sector.

5.2.5. Corporate initiatives

De Drie Mollen - coffee

De Drie Mollen Holding Company, established in 2012, is a global investment platform for coffee with its aim of delivering superior long-term shareholder returns. The company places a strong emphasis on business ethics, becoming a member of the UN Global Compact in 2022 and incorporating its Ten Principles into its strategy, policies, and procedures. De Drie Mollen has set high standards for Business Ethics Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), including the implementation of key policies and comprehensive training on ethical business practices. This commitment reflects the company's dedication to responsible and sustainable business operations (De Drie Mollen, 2023).

Unilever

Unilever is a consumer goods company, with many well-established brands under its belt. The company's reach is so great it is available in every country (Unilever, 2023). As such, it plays a significant role in agrifood value chains. They claim to want to make "sustainable living more commonplace". Two documents make up their sustainable sourcing programme; the Unilever Sustainable Agriculture Code (SAC) and the Unilever Regenerative Agriculture Principles. The former document makes use of the term Biodiversity Action Plan (BAP), which they borrow from the CBD, and they describe as "any kind of conservation plan and biodiversity management system, so long as it fulfils the three key actions that are recommended by the Sustainable Agriculture Code implementation guide." (Unilever, 2017a). This wide definition redirects one to the implementation guide: a 200+ page document where the key actions are not clearly defined. However, this document asks farmers in the Unilever supply chain to "engage in programmes that link their farming activities with benefits to biodiversity and/or ecosystem service provision." (Unilever, 2017a). Here, biodiversity and ecosystem services are used interchangeably and are not defined. Moreover, there are no clear guidelines or mandates on what these practices entails nor measuring metrics. Alongside the SAC, the Regenerative Agriculture Principles "provide guidance on how to further deliver positive outcomes in terms of nourishing the soil, increasing biodiversity, improving water quality and climate resilience, capturing carbon and restoring and regenerating the land". Unilever claims these principles will be implemented with "a suite of Lighthouse projects to trial". However, so far, no legitimacy, certification nor monitoring of these principles for producers have been drafted (Unilever, 2021).

Table 8 Biodiversity principles and metrics according to Unilever's Regenerative Agriculture Principles (Unilever, 2021)

Principles	Regenerative metrics
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Do not convert natural habitats 2. Create conditions and apply practices which increase plant and animal species numbers 3. Create specific habitats for predatory insects which can control pest insects 4. Only apply crop protection practices which have no influence on non-target species 5. Apply planting patterns which avoid monotony (e.g. intercropping, strip farming, pixel farming) 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 6. Number and variety of crops in the rotation 7. Number and abundance of species, i.e. insects, earthworms, birds, rodents, predatory birds 8. Presence of landscape elements which provide habitats for animal species (e.g. field margins, ponds, hedges, windrows, shadow trees, pockets of forest or coppice) 9. Soil microbial biomass and diversity

Protection of smallholders is also explored in the Regenerative Agriculture Principles document. It follows a similar structure to that of biodiversity, whereby principles are presented, and numerical

metrics are given for measuring their success. The subjects of these livelihood principles are smallholder farmers, and the objective is to train these producers in regenerative agriculture. 'Equity' is not mentioned, and neither are other similar terms, on the Regenerative Agriculture Principles. However, this term is defined in terms of biodiversity offsets in the SAC implementation guide (Unilever, 2017b) as such: "A biodiversity offset should be designed and implemented in an equitable manner, which means the sharing among stakeholders of the rights and responsibilities, risks and rewards associated with a project and offset in a fair and balanced way, respecting legal and customary arrangements. Special consideration should be given to respecting both internationally and nationally recognised rights of indigenous peoples and local communities" (p. 97). Here, contextual equity is granted to historically marginalised groups (IPLCs). Later in the same document, gender is also a matter of equity discussion, where the company pledges to gather data on gender disparities "to be able to demonstrate our commitment to improvements in the professionalism and training in our supply chains, and as evidence of the commitment of those working in our supply chains to promote gender equity." (Unilever, 2017, p. 224).

5.2.6 Pricing strategies

Tony Chocoloney

Tony Chocoloney is a Dutch chocolate company which uses a combination of lobbying, fair trade certification + living income and true pricing to promote a more sustainable and equitable chocolate sector, within its sourcing environment and beyond. They aim to make "100% slave free the norm in chocolate", shedding light on the power and value imbalances in chocolate supply chains, particularly at the farmer's level. They go as far as denouncing the cocoa supply chain as a form of modern slavery (Tony's Chocoloney, 2023a). Moreover, the company is committed to minimise the negative impacts of cocoa production on the climate, tracking producers to make sure no protected areas are being misused for agricultural production and promoting agroforestry and reforestation (Tony's Chocoloney, 2023b). Tony's Chocoloney's annual report asserts the link between social justice and climate justice, and thus are committed to tracing its products to reduce deforestation and carbon emissions in their supply chain as a further commitment to farmer's and planetary well-being (Tony's Chocoloney, 2023b). In the year 2020, Tony's Chocoloney began its 'Tony's Open Chain' initiative, which they describe as "an industry-led, collaborative initiative to transform cocoa supply chains" (Tony's Chocoloney, 2023b, p. 60). In this initiative, eight companies (ranging from supermarkets to chain suppliers) pledge to raise consumer awareness and spread the company's message.

Nespresso

Nespresso's AAA Sustainable Quality Program is a sourcing initiative "designed to ensure the continued supply of high-quality coffee while improving the livelihoods of farmers and their communities, and protecting the environment." (Nespresso, 2023) Launched alongside the Rainforest Alliance in 2003, the program was formed out of an acknowledgement of the many socio ecological challenges coffee production often carries. The AAA program is based upon three pillars; quality, productivity and sustainability. In this project, social and environmental goals are weighed equally. The program encompasses three interventions; farm management -though the empowerment of farmers to take on sustainable quality agricultural practices such as regenerative agriculture and agroforestry-, community resilience -encouraging the development of solutions for communities and landscapes in the face of climate change- and through wider systemic solutions -which is defined as the "Leverage the collective resources of farmer organisations, academics, municipalities and governments to address wider coffee sector challenges." (Nespresso, 2023; Rainforest Alliance, 2021b). Sustainability and biodiversity are often spoken of in the context of this project, yet they are never clearly defined. The Rainforest Alliance 2010-2020 impact report claims land and water conservation initiatives have taken place as part of their joint project (Rainforest Alliance, 2021b). In terms of leveraging systemic change, the same report notes that governmental interaction has taken the shape of governance and the facilitation of roundtable discussions with governments in producer countries, as well as using existing government instruments (such as Colombia's PES scheme) to help farmers sustain themselves (Rainforest Alliance, 2023). Moreover, thanks to the Rainforest Alliance-Nespresso collaboration, many farmers from the Nespresso value

chain have funnelled into Rainforest Alliance and Fairtrade International certifications (Nespresso, 2023).

LIDL

The German supermarket chain LIDL, under its tag line “A better tomorrow”, commits itself to partake in responsible sourcing of its products. In order to foster sustainability across the business, they “[are] fully committed to ensuring that our buying power is driving positive change for producers, communities and the environment as a whole” (LIDL, 2023a). As part of this project, LIDL prioritises EU Leaf certified products, local sourcing in European stores and exclusively sources fruits and vegetables from Bord Bia Sustainable Horticulture Assurance Scheme (SHAS) and/or certified to the GLOBALGAP Fruit and Vegetable standard (LIDL, 2023a). The latter is a certification system that LIDL has collaborated with to include their own biodiversity standard (LIDL, 2023b). Moreover, they have published position papers on the sustainable sourcing of palm oil (LIDL, 2017) and Human Rights and Environmental Due Diligence Policy For the responsible sourcing of products (LIDL, 2020).

True Price

True Price has a unique approach whereby it brings together consumers, business and institutions to “take action in incorporating environmental and social costs in prices” (True Price, 2023a). They describe themselves as “the market plus the environmental and social costs”. (True Price, 2023a). Founded in 2012, True Price began as a research endeavour to measure the monetary ‘costs’ of the socioecological toll food production takes along the supply chain (True Price, 2023b). True Price evolved into a non-profit in 2018, facilitating others to put true prices into practice in supermarkets, school canteens and supply chains (True Price, 2023b).

5.4 Summary

In this section, we first introduced different market approaches to tackle sustainability challenges within the agri-food system. Subsequently, some examples of each strategy were presented. Throughout these initiatives, there are widely different understandings of **biodiversity** present. Only the RSPO gives a definition, explaining that biodiversity, or the variety of life, forms the foundation of the health of ecosystem services and allows for ecosystems to adjust to disturbances (resiliency). [To RSPO,] conservation of biodiversity includes the preservation of rare, threatened, and endangered species, and preservation of High Value Conservation areas.” (RSPO 2018). In all other instances, biodiversity is mentioned as a result of alternative framing methods (e.g.: IDH, GCP, POIG) or as an instrumental factor in socio ecological resilience (e.g.: Rainforest Alliance). In all cases, in the Markets actor group biodiversity is always understood in *relation* to practices, not as an intrinsic good. Moreover, biodiversity conservation starts and ends at the producer level; processing, transporting, trade and so on are hardly ever addressed.

In terms of **equity**, Fairtrade International is the only initiative to give a definition, whereas most other market actors mention equity in some capacity (see Table X). Out of the reviewed initiatives, Fairtrade and Tony’s Chocolonely are the most committed to promoting equity, placing biodiversity as a second objective. The former frames equity as a human rights issue. Tony’s Chocolonely is the most radical in its callout of the inequity issues within the cocoa value chain, claiming to fight modern-day slavery. POIG and Tony’s Chocolonely are the only actors to acknowledge the devastating socio ecological impact the palm oil and cocoa industries have had historically; all other market actors do not take accountability. This lack of contextual equity is particularly stark with large multi-nationals such as Nespresso and Unilever, where a small section of their operations are moving towards more sustainable initiatives, whilst a large percentage of their production chain remains largely unchanged.

The fact that private organizations are less clear about their definitions and operationalizations of concepts such as biodiversity and equity can be logically explained by the idea that they need public organizations to legitimise their actions in these domains. The contributions that private organizations can make to the transition is how markets and the companies in these markets can change their processes to reach the biodiversity and equity goals while remaining profitable.

Table 9 Definitions of Biodiversity and Equity in the market and private sector governance pathway

Initiative	Definitions - Biodiversity	Definitions - Equity
Fairtrade International	<p><i>Of all approaches, agroecology is most aligned with Fairtrade's mission, vision, and Theory of Change. It explicitly addresses core Fairtrade topics such as social justice, biodiversity, and empowering vulnerable or marginalised rural producers.</i></p> <p>(Fairtrade, 2023)</p>	<p><i>Equity – recognizing the rights and responsibilities of all members towards furthering the objectives of the Association in relation to their capacity to do so.</i></p> <p><i>Justice – recognizing the responsibilities of all members towards the prevention and elimination of unfair trade practices affecting Fairtrade Producers.</i></p> <p>(Fairtrade, 2022)</p>
Rainforest Alliance	<p><i>"biodiversity as a critical element of ecosystem and social resilience."</i></p> <p>(Rainforest Alliance, 2021a)</p>	<p><i>Strong local grassroots organisations also play an important role in community equity. In general, the more vertical integration and diversification that takes place within community forest enterprises, the more social inclusion is present, as more employment is typically created. Specific efforts are needed to engage the poor, women, and youth in improving equity in tenure, community governance, community forest enterprise management and operations, and benefit sharing, as well as to improve gender equality and women's empowerment. (Rainforest Alliance, 2021a)</i></p>
RSPO	<p><i>Biodiversity Protected: Biodiversity, or the variety of life, forms the foundation of the health of ecosystem services and allows for ecosystems to adjust to disturbances (resiliency). Conservation of biodiversity includes the preservation of rare, threatened, and endangered species, and preservation of HCV areas. (RSPO 2018)</i></p>	<p><i>Goal: "Provide training on organisation governance that establishes gender-equitable principles of leadership and decision-making (quotas)."</i></p> <p><i>"Gender-responsive leadership and transparent group governance are critical to ensure the equitable distribution of benefits, whether in mixed or women-only groups."</i></p>
IDH	<p>Addressed through Zero-Deforestation initiatives, not defined.</p>	<p>Gender transformative approach.</p> <p>Integration of forest-dependent communities and farmers through sustainable livelihood practices.</p>
Global Coffee Platform	<p><i>Producers protect and restore natural resources including biodiversity, soil and water, are better able to adapt to climate change and are remunerated for environmental services provided to society. (GCP, 2020)</i></p>	<p><i>Producers support diversity, equity, inclusion through participation and development opportunities for all in coffee farming and management.</i></p> <p><i>Gender equity and social inclusion (GESI) analysis is conducted to identify the needs, participation rates, access to resources and development, control of assets, decision-making powers, etc. of women, youth and marginalised groups. (GCP, 2020)</i></p>

Initiative	Definitions - Biodiversity	Definitions - Equity
Palm Oil Innovation Group	Addressed alongside 'carbon conservation' -> <i>The link between oil palm expansion and deforestation will be broken through undertaking an HCV-HCSA assessment, and a process of obtaining Free, Prior and Informed Consent (FPIC) to use land. The approach combines biodiversity and carbon conservation, as well as social considerations (including community needs).</i> (POIG, 2019) <i>Wildlife conservation: Management plans for all rare, threatened or endangered species include actions for their protection, survival, and prevention of poaching, in the landscape outside the management area.</i> (POIG, 2019)	<i>A comprehensive social programme with regular monitoring is in operation to ensure palm oil production does not result in human rights violations, trigger social conflicts, or produce 'land grabbing', and addresses key social equity issues including housing, healthcare, education and empowerment of women.</i> (POIG, 2019)
Unilever	<i>Biodiversity action plan: "any kind of conservation plan and biodiversity management system, so long as it fulfils the three key actions that are recommended by the Sustainable Agriculture Code implementation guide."</i> (SAC2017)	<i>"the sharing among stakeholders of the rights and responsibilities, risks and rewards associated with a project and offset in a fair and balanced way, respecting legal and customary arrangements. Special consideration should be given to respecting both internationally and nationally recognised rights of indigenous peoples and local communities"</i> (SAC2017)
Tony's Chocolonely	N/A	Argumentation around human rights and decent standard of living: "A decent standard of living is a Human Right. Human rights violations must include more than child labour and modern slavery. The way companies purchase should enable farmers to earn a living income."
The Sustainability Consortium	N/A	N/A
Nespresso	Presented as one of the 'three levers of action, but not defined as such. Ecosystems approach: "Supporting an agriculture that is mindful of the natural ecosystems around coffee farms and that protects the habitats of species whilst conserving biodiversity and water sources." (Nespresso, 2023)	N/A
True Price	N/A	N/A
Lidl	Instrumental to the maintenance of ecosystems: "The loss of biodiversity poses an existential threat to ecosystems. As a food supplier, Lidl is aware of its responsibility to preserve ecosystems." (Lidl, 2023b)	N/A

6. Civil society & non-governmental organisation initiatives, social and ecological movements

In this chapter, three different actor groups will be explored: BINGOS, small environmental NGOs, and social movements. BINGOS are described by the IUCN as big, international, non-governmental organisations (thus forming the acronym BINGO) (Menton and Gilbert, 2021). For the purpose of this project, we focus on environmental BINGOS, particularly on their take on and understanding of food systems sustainability. We look at WWF, Greenpeace and Friends of the Earth. Following, the smaller environmental NGOs discussed in this section were chosen due to their explicit focus on transforming agrifood systems. These are EnvolVert, GRAIN and ASEED. Lastly, two social movements will be presented: La Via Campesina and SlowFood Europe. Out of the large number of social movements regarding food systems, we chose to focus on these two since they are popular movements with a strong online presence, both having a clear mission statement and manifesto of sorts that we could analyse as part of the corpus. These three sub-groups comprise the actor group 'NGOs and Social Movements'.

6.1. BINGOs

6.1.1. WWF

World Wildlife Fund (WWF) is one of the largest conservation non-governmental organisations in existence. The organisation has been a leader in the sector for nearly 60 years. Although in its inception WWF focused on wildlife conservation, it has since expanded their goals to climate, forests, oceans and food issues. (WWF, 2023a). The organisation takes on a very scientific approach to their biodiversity definition, describing it as the conglomeration of living things that inhabit an area, but taking it a step further by adding that "*Biodiversity supports everything in nature that we need to survive: food, clean water, medicine, and shelter*" (WWF, 2023b), thus stressing human's dependency on other life forms to sustain our own. WWF is consistent in this conceptualization across reports; in their 2022 Living Planet report (WWF, 2022), they stress that "*To nourish future generations, food systems must be in balance with nature and help conserve and restore biodiversity and a stable climate. They must underpin equitable livelihoods and the health and well-being of producers, communities, and economies.*". Thus, in the context of food systems, biodiversity and equity are both vital components. WWF does not offer a straightforward definition of equity but uses this term alongside 'social well-being' often, placing particular emphasis on women's rights (WWF, 2021).

6.1.2 GreenPeace

For over half a century, Greenpeace has investigated and condemned environmental degradation at the hands of industry and political negligence (Greenpeace, 2023a). The NGO's principle goal is to "protect biodiversity in all its forms", although they give no definition of what the term means (Greenpeace, 2023b). In their annual report, Greenpeace envisions "a planet where it is understood and accepted that the fates of humanity and the natural world are inextricably linked; and therefore economic, cultural and political systems are designed to deliver sustainability, justice and equity for all peoples and the planet" (Greenpeace, 2023b). The report exemplifies this interlinked nature, where human and more-than-human rights are addressed jointly, stating that ""Assuring planet sustainability with equity and justice can easily seem an insurmountable task with all we need to do", but that it is paramount for a just future (Greenpeace, 2023b). Equity plays a core role in Greenpeace's mission, with their first two principles addressing the need for 1) an equitable, diverse and inclusive Greenpeace and 2) Equity, diversity and inclusion reflect our core organisational values and our moral values as human beings. (Greenpeace, 2023b). Beyond their corporate values, equity plays a role in their environmental actions; Greenpeace makes sure to address the historical inequality of climate change, highlighting how often nations that have historically contributed the least to GHG emissions are suffering most of the consequences, listing Small Pacific Island States and Pakistan as examples (Greenpeace, 2023, b).

6.1.3 Friends of the Earth

Friends of the Earth calls itself "the world's largest grassroots environmental federation" with the aim to create societies that live in peace and in harmony with nature (Friends of the Earth, 2023). In

a 2022 report, Friends of the Earth urged the UN for a need to integrate agriculture onto the CBD “due to its powerful role - both as a destructive force, and in its ability to nurture and restore biodiversity”. In this report, they describe biodiversity as more than a livelihood, but as *life itself*. The definition, as shown in **Table 10**, integrates equity and biodiversity in its recognition of the more-than instrumental values biodiversity poses within agriculture to “peasant farmers, Indigenous Peoples, fishers, forest dwellers, livestock keepers, and local communities”, taking no account too the historical role these marginalised peoples have played in the protection of life on earth (Friends of the Earth, 2022). Friends for the Earth argue that agroecology has the potential to achieve food security and biodiversity conservation goals alongside the rights and agency of all peoples. They argue, a post-2020 biodiversity framework “*at this very critical juncture for humanity and the planet, must fully reflect the magnitude of the biodiversity crisis, interlinked with the climate change, food and health systems crises. In order to confront these challenges, the CBD and all parties involved in the negotiations are obliged to deliver a bold and ambitious vision of a planet that will stem the tide of biodiversity loss, and renew its abundance, resulting in all peoples’ basic needs being met, and harmony and equity between all living beings.*” (Friends of the Earth, 2022). Thus, although no definition of equity is provided, it is clear Friends of the Earth see issues of biodiversity and equity as an interlinked and indivisible challenge which must be tackled jointly. Moreover, Friends of the Earth argues for equity between all living beings, expanding this concept beyond the human and advocating for intraspecies justice.

6.2. Environmental NGOs

6.2.1 EnvoVert

EnvoVert was established in 2011 with the goal to protect forests and biodiversity in rural areas of Latin America and France (EnvoVert, 2023). It promotes agroforestry as a means to conserve biodiversity yet offers no definition of what they consider to be biodiversity. It is an organisation with a strong human focus; in their 2022 report, Chairman Oliver Guichardon estates, “*Each project, through extraordinary human encounters, helps us bring further our vision of a society based on environmental and social justice, on the fair redistribution of wealth and, above all, on the respect of indigenous populations.*” (EnvoVert, 2022). In the absence of an equity definition, this quote gives way into the conceptualization EnvoVert gives to this word: equity involves distributive equity and historical acknowledgement of marginalised peoples. Moreover, they state community governance and capacity building as some of their means of action, reflecting an intention to address procedural justice in their projects.

6.2.2 GRAIN

Grain is an international NGO created with the goal to defend smallholder farmers’ rights and promote biodiversity-based food systems. They don’t offer a definition for biodiversity-based food systems, yet an analysis of the NGO’s reports and documents seems to suggest the focus is placed on seed biodiversity, and much of the advocacy surrounds crops’ genetic diversity. They propose agroecology for climate resilience and biodiversity conservation and claim to focus on climate justice although do not provide a working definition (GRAIN, 2022).

6.2.3 ASEED

The Action for Sustainability, Environment, Equality and Diversity (ASEED) is a European NGO based in The Netherlands which “aims to support and empower groups and individuals (especially youth) who are striving for fair and sustainable food systems” (ASEED, 2023). ASEED encourages a future for agriculture which is no longer dependent on fossil fuels, stating that “While it claims the opposite, it is clear that fossil fuel-based industrial agriculture cannot feed the world, because it relies on a variety of finite resources and is destroying the very foundations of life itself: healthy soils, biodiversity, agricultural diversity, and a stable climate” (ASEED, 2021). Moreover, this has consequences not only on food security but in people’s lives: “The devastating consequences cannot be ignored any longer: runaway climate change, ecological collapse, impoverishment of farmers and the destruction of rural communities” (ASEED, 2021). Instead, they pledge for agro-ecological farms which “can promote biodiversity and soil health, use less water resources, are resilient for the shocks of a changing climate, offer the possibility to capture carbon in the living soil and can provide dignified compensation to farmers.” (ASEED, 2021). Whilst they do not provide a direct definition for biodiversity, ASEED addresses environmental and human concerns of industrial

agriculture and climate change jointly, seeing them as indiscernible from one another. Moreover, they do not use the equity language opting instead for an intersectional approach to organising which “provides possibilities to reduce power inequalities, exclusion and marginalisation within and across progressive movements” (ASEED; 2023). In this intersectional framework, many of the principles of equity are featured, such as the centring of voices at the margins of society and acknowledging the systemic oppression of certain peoples and contextual equity.

6.3. Social Movements

6.3.1 La Vía Campesina

La Vía Campesina (LVC) is a food sovereignty movement which was founded in the early 90s by non-governmental organisations of the Global South with the goals to “build an international movement capable of giving voice and resonance to peasants worldwide, united by their rejection of the neoliberal model of rural development and their determination to be included in shaping public policies affecting them.” (LVC, 2023). The movement has since then grown to reach 81 countries across four continents, including Europe. In celebration of thirty years of activism, LVC published a political declaration where they divulge their stances on biodiversity and equity. LVC demands Peasant Agroecology is scaled up “*as a solution to climate crisis, loss of biodiversity and soil fertility*”, challenges which the document states are a direct result of unsustainable agricultural practices (LVC, 2022). LVC has a history of conceptualising biodiversity as a more-than-scientific concept, stating in the year 200 that for LVC “*biodiversity is not only flora, fauna, earth, water and ecosystems; it is also cultures, systems of production, human and economic relations, forms of government; in essence it is freedom.*” (LVC, 2000). This is a holistic and complex definition which even decades ago exceeds the scope of definitions offered by present-day international policy instruments, merging concepts of biodiversity and equity as inherently intertwined. LVC continues to defend such an approach to biodiversity to this day, with representative speakers at the 2022 COP stating that “Every time those in power fail to uphold the human and collective rights of the best custodians of biodiversity [, IPLCs and peasants], you fail to uphold your duty to protect biodiversity.” (Jonas, 2022).

Equity is not defined in their political declaration, yet it is very much present. As a movement which places social justice and dignity at the heart of their ethos, they acknowledge the historical injustices peasants have endured. As such, they set two goals which directly tackle issues of equity; to “build and strengthen inclusiveness against violence and oppression” and to “Build Peasant and Popular Feminism to define and shape gender relations in our movement, and as a political tool against all forms of violence.” (LVC, 2022).

6.3.2 Slow Food Europe

Born in the 1980s from a group of European activists, Slow Food Europe is a movement which “aims to defend regional traditions, good food, gastronomic pleasure and a slow pace of life [...] embracing a comprehensive approach to food that recognizes the strong connections between plate, planet, people, politics and culture” (Slow Food, 2023). Their three tenets for quality food, which encompass the movement’s philosophy, are 1) good (flavour), 2) clean (production) and 3) fair (processes). Point 2 addresses biodiversity as an integral part that must be taken into consideration to “safeguard the health of the consumer and the producer” (Slow Food, n.d.). They speak of biodiversity as “our insurance policy for the future, allowing plants and animals to adapt to climatic changes, attacks by parasites and disease, or the unexpected,” thus conceptualising it as a tool for food safety and human well being. Point 3 tackles the social issues associated with food production, where “Social justice should be pursued through the creation of conditions of labour respectful of man and his rights and capable of generating adequate rewards; through the pursuit of balanced global economies; through the practice of sympathy and solidarity; through respect for cultural diversities and traditions.” (Slow Food, n.d.) Notably, equity is not mentioned in strategic plans nor their manifesto. The manifesto moreover refers to humanity as “*man and his rights*’ , using a language which excludes non-male persons.

6.4. Summary

In this chapter, we presented examples of social movements and NGOs in the European Union which engage with civil society and stakeholders along value chains to tackle agrifood challenges

and GreenPeace are large international NGOs concerned with biodiversity conservation and fighting climate change respectively yet mobilise a substantial amount of their efforts towards promoting sustainability in the agricultural sector as part of their goals. La Via Campesina, GRAIN and ASEED are primarily peasant and small-farmer social movements and organisations focused on putting equity and justice at the forefront of their missions which range in geographical focus and scale. **Slow Food Europe** brings a culinary lens to food production in Europe, whereas **Friends of the Earth** is strong in its climate justice approach.

Table 10 Definitions of Biodiversity and Equity in the Actor Group NGOs & Civil Society

Initiative	Definitions - Biodiversity	Definitions - Equity
WWF	"Biodiversity is all the different kinds of life you'll find in one area—the variety of animals, plants, fungi, and even microorganisms like bacteria that make up our natural world. Each of these species and organisms work together in ecosystems, like an intricate web, to maintain balance and support life. Biodiversity supports everything in nature that we need to survive: food, clean water, medicine, and shelter." (WWF, 2023b)	"Human and social values: protecting and improving rural and coastal livelihoods, equity and social well-being is essential for sustainable food systems " (WWF, 2021) "[Landscape approach] requires farmers to be able to design and voice their own solutions, protect their rights, improve livelihoods and promote equity, justice and social well-being, particularly for women." (WWF, 2021)
Friends Of The Earth	"For family farmers and peasants, agricultural biodiversity is more than a livelihood; it is life itself. Peasant farmers, Indigenous Peoples, fishers, forest dwellers, livestock keepers, and local communities see themselves as part of nature, and part of the evolutionary circle of biodiversity. Their everyday acts both benefit from and nourish biodiversity and the ecosystems around them. For thousands of years, they have used the wisdom gained from experience, knowledge, culture, tradition and love of their territories, to shape and enhance the diversity of their crops and their wild relatives; tended their lands, waters and territories; and raised rare animal and aquatic breeds that are only kept alive in their care."	"Agroecology is a visionary framework and a key pathway to climate and food systems resilience, with agricultural biodiversity and human rights as its centrepieces. It is rapidly growing as a viable response to the climate and biodiversity crises, with equally important dimensions of the rights and agency of peasants, gender equity, and the engagement of youth and the next generation of farmers."
GreenPeace	"Strives to protect biodiversity in all its forms" (but does not define it)	"Our vision: We imagine a planet where it is understood and accepted that the fates of humanity and the natural world are inextricably linked; and therefore economic, cultural and political systems are designed to deliver sustainability, justice and equity for all peoples and the planet"
GRAIN	biodiversity-based agriculture"; Protecting seed's genetic diversity through land ownership and food sovereignty Agroecology for climate resilience and biodiversity conservation	Focus on climate justice, undefined
ASEED	Not defined – Promote a fossil-fuel-free agrifood system.	Focus on intersectionality: " an intersectional approach to organising provides possibilities to reduce power inequalities, exclusion and marginalisation within and across progressive movements" (ASEED, 2019)
La Via Campesina	"biodiversity is not only flora, fauna, earth, water and ecosystems; it is also cultures, systems of production, human and economic relations, forms of government; in essence it is freedom."	"We reject this neoliberal model that runs counter to our collective vision of harmony with nature, unity and peace. We affirm our commitment to continue to build democratic societies against imperialism. Over the last 30 years, together with our allies, we have been collectively building hope and solidarity through food sovereignty putting humanity, Mother Earth and social justice at the centre."
SlowFood Europe	"At its essence it signifies nature, life itself, and the diversity of life on many levels - from the smallest and most basic (like genes and bacteria) to animal and plant species, up to the most complex levels (ecosystems). All these levels intersect and influence each other and each other's evolution."	"Social justice should be pursued through the creation of conditions of labour respectful of man and his rights and capable of generating adequate rewards; through the pursuit of balanced global economies; through the practice of sympathy and solidarity; through respect for cultural diversities and traditions"

7. Discussion and conclusions

In this chapter, we compare the diverse transformative change governance pathways on how they conceive the terms of biodiversity and equity among the different stakeholders in each of the pathways. Most of the different governance pathways (International, regional, marketing and private initiatives, social movements and NGOs) presented and which we identified as key stakeholders in the EU for promoting agrifood systems transformations, have introduced the concepts of biodiversity and equity through a wide range of strategies, policies, instruments, mechanisms, discourses and practices.

Overall, there exists a consensus related with the **“biodiversity”** definition, which is mainly based on the definition provided by the CBD in 1992, which states that *“Biological diversity means the variability among living organisms from all sources including, inter alia, terrestrial, marine and other aquatic ecosystems and the ecological complexes of which they are part: this includes diversity within species, between species and of ecosystems.”* (CBD, 1992).

On the contrary, the concept of **“equity”** is being used to refer to a broader range of concepts and definitions, which could differ among the diverse governance pathways (International, regional, and private initiatives, social movements and NGOs) and stakeholders. These differences in conceptualization might impact the strategies, policies, instruments, mechanisms, discourses and practices implemented by diverse stakeholders for promoting equity within the food-systems. In broad terms, seldom was there an actor which engaged with all three dimensions of McDermott and Mahanty's (2013) equity framework: **distributive equity, procedural equity and contextual equity**. Notably, the EU actor group lacks behind the most in including equity in their texts. In addition to the definition of biodiversity presented by the CBD (1992), the governance pathway of **international governance and policy agreements (SDGs, OCDE, UN, WTO, FAO, IPBES, IPCC)** adds the concept of genetic diversity in the majority of the documents that were reviewed. The importance of genetic diversity in seeds was asserted following the same 1992 convention. Equity discussions were largely missing from the IP narrative. Nonetheless, two entities stood out as diverging from the rest; IPBES and IPCC both showcase an approach which places much more emphasis on equity than the other reviewed documents. This distinction became apparent through the qualitative analysis of the documents, were it was found the IPBES Global Assessment Report and IPCC AR6 were the only documents -alongside the IFAD strategy on biodiversity- in the International Policy Actor group which either directly mentioned equity or applied equity principles throughout the text.

In the IPBES Global assessment report, equity was mentioned but not explicitly defined. It was most often mentioned in relation to inequity, described by the authors as “an unequal access to material goods” (IPBES, 2019), a definition aligned with what McDermott and Mahanty (2013) coined the distributive core of equity. Sustainability is moreover addressed with a strong equity component; they argue, in line with McDermott and Mahanty's procedural equity, that “Promoting inclusive governance approaches through stakeholder engagement and the inclusion of indigenous peoples and local communities to ensure equity and participation” (IPBES, 2019). Moreover, IPBES acknowledges the historical marginalisation of certain peoples and knowledge systems, in particular that of indigenous peoples and local communities (IPLC) (contextual equity). McElwee et al (2020) claim this is the first global scale assessment to “systematically engage with [Indigenous and Local Knowledge] and issues of concert to IPLCs”.

The IPCC report dedicates an entire chapter to Equity and Inclusion in CC Action, noting that “Actions that prioritise equity, climate justice, social justice and inclusion lead to more sustainable outcomes, co-benefits, reduce trade-offs, support transformative change and advance climate-resilient development” (IPCC, 2023, p. 66). In the IPCC's definition of equity (Table X), distributive equity encompasses goods and ills, noting historic responsibility (contextual equity) to produce such ills. Moreover, participation in decision-making (procedural equity) is stressed.

The explicit mention of marginalised groups, specially LCIPs in both texts, is particularly striking considering other IP documents fail to mention them. At most, such as in the case of the IFAD Strategy on Biodiversity (IFAD, 2022), equity is measured with indicators and expressed merely in terms of distributive justice. Moreover, equity and social justice does not bridge over to issues of

biodiversity in other texts, perpetuating the Cartesian divide between social and ecological issues as stark, distinct categories (Aldeia and Alves, 2019). This dualistic thinking has been hypothesised by many scholars to be at the root of the systematic inability to tackle the unsustainability of food systems (Nasr, 2023; Goodman, 2017). On this front, only IPBES offers a definition of biodiversity which acknowledges humans as an indispensable part of ecosystems, going as far as opening its definition to include non-western conceptualizations and valuations of 'nature', such as Mother Earth and Pachamama (IPBES, 2019) (See Table X).

Overall, the discourse of the International Policy actor group is rather consistent in its expression of biodiversity as an instrumental good of scientific importance. In governance systems, values of biodiversity have only been included as instrumental values, with the above IPBES description being an outlier (Diaz et al., 2015). There is more diversity surrounding what equity entails, although overwhelmingly distributive equity and intergenerational equity -particularly in relation to climate change- were the most present out of McDermott and Mahanty's (2013) framework. Equity and diversity were consistently described as separate terms with very little overlap. IPBES and IPCC, as science-based advisory instruments, are outliers in this group, opting for a pluralistic conception of biodiversity.

The **EU actor group** is quite consistent in its messages, given the EU follows similar guidelines along its governing bodies. However, clear differences can be observed; Within the European Green Deal documents, there exist clear disparities in the ways biodiversity and equity are written into policy and tackled. The EU Biodiversity strategy is the only document to define what constitutes biodiversity, noting: "From the world's great rainforests to small parks and gardens, from the blue whale to microscopic fungi, biodiversity is the extraordinary variety of life on Earth. We humans are part of, and fully dependent on, this web of life: it gives us the food we eat, filters the water we drink, and supplies the air we breathe. Nature is as important for our mental and physical wellbeing as it is for our society's ability to cope with global change, health threats and disasters. We need nature in our lives" (European Commission, 2020a, p.1.). Here, multiple valuations of biodiversity are presented. However, in the accompanying documents which make up the EU Green Deal, biodiversity takes on a much less nuanced meaning. Although these documents reference one another and point back to the Biodiversity Strategy, in the F2F and CAP documents biodiversity is mainly spoken of as something which we must stop from further deteriorating; reasoning and strategies are loosely defined if at all present. In the CAP, agriculture is framed in a farming context, whereas the F2F strategy does not specify any further. In terms of equity, the Biodiversity Strategy only makes mention of it in relation to the UN convention on genetic diversity (UN, 1992). The F2F strategy speaks of equity once: "The European Green Deal is an opportunity to reconcile our food system with the needs of the planet and to respond positively to Europeans' aspirations for healthy, equitable and environmentally friendly food" (European Commission, 2020b). Here, equity is understood only as a matter of food security, and the issues of equity in the food production chains, distribution of environmental goods and ill or fair wages are not addressed. The trade agreements with producer countries are similarly silent on issues of biodiversity and equity, despite the claim in the F2F strategy and other Green Deal documents that the EU would make strides towards ensuring imported products in the EU meet certain environmental and sustainable development standards. These standards are all but uncertain in the trade agreements with Colombia, Kenya and Cameroon. Despite academics claiming the EU is undergoing a transformation in bilateral trade agreements towards more environmentally conscious agreements (McNeill, 2020), it seems these changes have not yet reached the negotiation tables when it comes to these three producer countries.

In the **market and private sector** actor group, a wide variety of approaches to sustainability were showcased. Many lean heavily on alternative farming systems; FairTrade is a strong proponent of agroecology, whereas Unilever has, in recent years, developed a 'regenerative agriculture' approach. These two market initiatives differ largely in size and thus value chain length: whilst FairTrade has a closer relationship with smallholder producers, the sheer scale of Unilever involves many more degrees of separation from producer to shelved produce, leading to much scepticism from academics and NGOs (Tittonell et al., 2022; Rivera-Ferre, 2018).

These initiatives focus mainly on improving sustainability at the very first step of the supply chain by targeting farmers. Through the promotion of farming practices such as agroforestry or net-zero deforestation commitments (E.g. IDH), using market language such as "carbon conservation" (e.g.:POIG), market actors are seemingly attempting, through private sector mechanisms, to

implement environmentally and socially conscious practices in the supply chains of highly demanded imported food products. A large motivator for shifting practices is the growing demand for sustainable products from consumers (). Issues of traceability and legitimacy have been noted by academics and must be acknowledged; Marin-Burgos et al., (2015) explored the perceived legitimacy of RSPO programs among local farmers in Colombia, finding the interventions often failed to take into account local politics, exacerbated inequalities and were mistrusted. Pascual et al. (2021) denounce the "accept[ance] and thus legitimization of] private (for profit) corporations as legitimate actors even where their rights to territory are acquired from corrupt institutional state structures, using methods that do not reflect local needs and rights" (Pascual et al. 2021). Since producers are located in developing countries, these market mechanisms invest their efforts mainly overseas. Additionally, traceability and scale of these hyper-local sustainable production programmes such as Nespresso's AAA project and certification schemes remain an issue (Hamann et al., 2014; Tionell et al., 2023; Sumberg et al., 2023; Panwar et al., 2023). These initiatives, especially those focused on certification and premium pricing, are focused on adding value to a product in the eyes of a consumer. Given as markets are profit-driven, it is unsurprising these initiatives often target shifting consumer habits. An example of how markets seek to content an ever-growing eco-conscious group of consumers is De Drie Mollen, where consumers themselves dictate supply rather directly.

Although each initiative discussed in this report uses specific language and slightly different approaches, it is a relatively cohesive group of actors. All initiatives discussed 'biodiversity', either in terms of 'preventing loss' or 'conserving'. They strongly favoured instrumental notions of biodiversity, where biodiversity conservation was not a goal in itself but a bi-product of their proposed alternative farming methods, or a key instrument in human wellbeing. Relational and intrinsic valuations of biodiversity were therefore not found. Some, such as POIG, LIDL and Tony's Chocolonely did acknowledge the historical and current role the production of agrifood commodities has played in biodiversity loss. This silence is particularly striking when it comes to large multinationals such as Unilever and Nespresso, who have both been under fire due to their unsustainable and socially damaging practices. These criticisms have come from academia as well as civil society and NGOs, as we shall later see.

Some initiatives reflected on the need for greater equity, although none of the initiatives expressed the ways in which markets might have created or further perpetuated these inequalities except for Tony's Chocolonely, who position themselves as antagonists to the 'modern slavery' of the chocolate industry (Tony's Chocolonely, 2023a). Likewise, Fairtrade prioritises equity and justice for smallholders. Other actors, such as IDH and GCP, do not focus on equality but are partial to discourse on gender instead, choosing to address the empowerment of women in the sector.

Lastly the **NGO actor group** encompasses stakeholders of varying size and influence; on the one hand, big international NGOs such as WWF and GreenPeace are primarily environmental NGOs, and so it'd be expected these entities would tackle the issue of sustainability in food systems as a primarily environmental issue. However, WWF and GreenPeace take on a socio-ecological approach; for WWF, context-based landscape approaches are the best solution for both biodiversity conservation and veiling for equity. Moreover, GreenPeace asserts that "*We imagine a planet where it is understood and accepted that the fates of humanity and the natural world are inextricably linked; and therefore economic, cultural and political systems are designed to deliver sustainability, justice and equity for all peoples and the planet*" (Greenpeace, 2023b). In the GreenPeace documents reviewed, they assert the need to protect biodiversity "in all its forms", however these plural visions of biodiversity are not expanded on further, maintaining an ambiguous focus. On the other hand, the NGO actor group also includes grassroots peasant movements; La Via Campesina, Friends of the Earth, GRAIN and ASEED. The first two are large NGOs of international recognition, whereas GRAIN operates mainly in South America and ASEED is based in The Netherlands. Despite differences in geographical scope, they take on a similar approach focused on amplifying farmers and peasant's voices and standing up against large agrifood corporations which, they argue, encourage unsustainable food practices and strip smallholders of rights and agency. Even with large NGOs like FOE, they frame biodiversity from a farmer's perspective: "*For family farmers and peasants, agricultural biodiversity is more than a livelihood; it is life itself. Peasant farmers, Indigenous Peoples, fishers, forest dwellers, livestock keepers, and local communities see themselves as part of nature, and part of the evolutionary circle of biodiversity. Their everyday acts both benefit from and nourish biodiversity and the ecosystems around them. For thousands of*

years, they have used the wisdom gained from experience, knowledge, culture, tradition and love of their territories, to shape and enhance the diversity of their crops and their wild relatives; tended their lands, waters and territories; and raised rare animal and aquatic breeds that are only kept alive in their care." (Friends of the Earth, 2022). This quote recontextualizes biodiversity, a term often discussed as a scientific, abstract concept in many policy documents and corporate jargon, and brings to the forefront the very real and life-defining relationship between food producers and non-human beings. Such a definition highlights how these grassroots movements place farmers and peasant rights at the core of their endeavours, many of their members being small-scale farmers activists. This section of NGOs is not afraid to be in direct conversation and often opposes other actors such as Market mechanisms and International Policies. For instance, a large-scale report by Friends of the Earth (Alonso-Fradejas, 2020) calls big corporations such as Unilever's 'regenerative agriculture principles' "junk agroecology"; an agroecology at the linchpin of politics, which meekly attempts to undo decades of socio-ecological deterioration at the hands of these very same large corporations. Alonso-Fradejas (2020) concludes that "the main global agrifood corporations are seeking to redress their worst socio-ecological impacts through the adoption of a model of sustainable agricultural intensification with agroecological nuances. This model seeks merely to introduce some required reforms to safeguard the current agrifood and corporate and industrial natural resource use systems from itself. The end goal of these reforms is to ensure that big business can continue profiting, without fundamentally transforming either the unjust socio-economic, political and ecological relations on which the agrifood system is based, or the exclusionary and short-sighted ideology that legitimises it.

References

- Abdih, Y. and Danninger, S. (2017), "What Explains the Decline of the U.S. Labor Share of Income? An Analysis of State and Industry Level Data", Working Paper WP/17/167, Washington (DC): International Monetary Fund
- Aldeia, J., & Alves, F. (2019). Against the environment. Problems in society/nature relations. *Frontiers in Sociology*, 4, 29.
- Alonso-Fradejas, A. (2020). Junk Agroecology': The corporate capture of agroecology for a partial ecological transition without social justice. ATI, TNI, Crocevia. This report was published in April 2020 as part of the 'Who Benefits?' series, with financial support from Bread for the World (Brot für die Welt). The opinions and views expressed herein are the sole responsibility of Friends of the Earth International, Transnational Institute and Crocevia. Published by: Friends of the Earth International, Transnational Institute and Crocevia. All rights reserved, 3
- Anthony, L. (2023). AntConc (Version 4.2.1) [Computer Software]. Tokyo, Japan: Waseda University. Available from <https://www.laurenceanthony.net/software.html>
- Arts, B. (2014). Assessing forest governance from a 'Triple C' perspective: Government, governance, governmentality. *Forest Policy and Economics*, 49, 17-22.
- Arts, B., Leroy, P., & Van Tatenhove, J. (2006). Political modernisation and policy arrangements: a framework for understanding environmental policy change. *Public organisation review*, 6, 93-106.
- ASEED Europe. (2021). "Annual Report 2020". Retrieved from <https://aseed.net/2020-aseed-annual-report/>
- ASEED Europe. (Accessed October 20, 2023). "Intersectionality statement". Retrieved from <https://aseed.net/intersectionality-statement/>
- Baker, P., Gabrielatos, C., Khosravini, M., Krzyżanowski, M., McEnery, T., & Wodak, R. (2008). A useful methodological synergy? Combining critical discourse analysis and corpus linguistics to examine discourses of refugees and asylum seekers in the UK press. *Discourse & society*, 19(3), 273-306.
- Behagel, J. (2012). The politics of democratic governance. The implementation of the water framework directive in the Netherlands.
- Butler, R. A. (2018). Logging – Tropical Rainforest Destruction. Retrieved from <https://rainforests.mongabay.com/0806.htm>.
- CBD (21 August 2021) First Draft of The Post-2020 Global Biodiversity Framework. United Nations. <https://www.cbd.int/doc/c/0037/8045/a67574c3f7452fd6bb56c058/wg2020-03-03-en.docx> .O
- CBD (5 December 2022). Recommendation Adopted by the Working Group on The Post-2020 Global Biodiversity Framework. United Nations. <https://www.cbd.int/doc/recommendations/wg2020-05/wg2020-05-rec-01-en.pdf>
- collective capabilities and societal learning". Geneva: International Labour Office. Retrieved from https://www.ilo.org/global/publications/books/WCMS_893832/lang--en/index.htm
- Cosme, I., Santos, R., & O'Neill, D. W. (2017). Assessing the degrowth discourse: A review and analysis of academic degrowth policy proposals. *Journal of cleaner production*, 149, 321-334.
- Covic, N., Dobermann, A., Fanzo, J., Henson, S., Herrero, M., Pingali, P., & Staal, S. (2021). All hat and no cattle: Accountability following the UN food systems summit. *Global Food Security*, 30, 100569.
- De Drie Mollen (Accessed November 18, 2023) "About De Drie Mollen". <https://www.dedriemollen.com/about/>
- Eakin, H., DeFries, R., Kerr, S., Lambin, E.F., Liu, J., Marcotullio, P.J., Messerli, P., Reenberg, A., Rueda, X., Swaffield, S.R. & Wicke, B., (2014). Significance of telecoupling for exploration of land-use change. In *Rethinking global land use in an urban era* (pp. 141-161). MIT Press.
- Eakin, H., Rueda, X., & Mahanti, A. (2017). Transforming governance in telecoupled food systems. *Ecology and Society*, 22(4).
- Elsby, M., Hobijn, B. and Sahin, A. (2013), "The Decline of the U.S. Labor Share", *Brookings papers on economic activity* 44(2):1-63.
- EnvolVert (2022). "Progress Report, 2022". EnvolVert.
- EnvolVert. (Accessed October 20, 2023). "Who are we?" Retrieved from <https://envolvert.org/en/organization/>
- Ericksen, P. J. (2008). Conceptualising food systems for global environmental change research. *Global Environmental Change*, 18, 234–245.
- Ericksen, P. J., Ingram, J. S. I., & Liverman, D. M. (2009). Food security and global environmental change: Emerging challenges. *Environmental Science and Policy*, 12(4), 373–377.
- European Commission (2019). "Communication From the Commission to the European Parliament, The Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions:

- The European Green Deal." Brussels, Belgium. Retrieved from <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=COM%3A2019%3A640%3AFIN>
- European Commission (2020a). "Communication From the Commission to the European Parliament, The Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions: EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030." Brussels, Belgium. Retrieved from <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A52020DC0380>
- European Commission (2020b). "Communication From the Commission to the European Parliament, The Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions: A Farm to Fork Strategy for a fair, healthy and environmentally-friendly food system." Brussels, Belgium. Retrieved from <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A52020DC0380>
- European Commission. (2023a). "Green Deal: New law to fight global deforestation and forest degradation driven by EU production and consumption enters into force". Retrieved from: https://environment.ec.europa.eu/news/green-deal-new-law-fight-global-deforestation-and-forest-degradation-driven-eu-production-and-2023-06-29_en.
- European Commission. (2023b). "Regulation (EU) 2023/1115 of the European Council and the Parliament of 31 May 2023 on the making available on the Union market and the export from the Union of certain commodities and products associated with deforestation and forest degradation and repealing Regulation (EU) No 995/2010". Brussels, Belgium. Retrieved from <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32023R1115>
- European Commission. (Accessed October 18, 2023). "Collective Economy". https://single-market-economy.ec.europa.eu/single-market/services/collaborative-economy_en
- European Union (EU) (September 2022). "Press Release. Policy Dialogues EU-Colombia, Ecuador, Perú on Sustainable Agriculture and Food Systems. Building Sustainable Food Systems Together." Retrieved from https://food.ec.europa.eu/horizontal-topics/farm-fork-strategy/international-dimension/eu-lac_en
- European Union (EU) (2012). Trade Agreement between the European Union and its Member States, of the one part, and Colombia and Peru, of the other part. European Union. http://data.europa.eu/eli/agree_international/2012/735/oj
- European Union (18 April, 2023). "Agri-Food Trade Statistical Factsheet. European Union – EPA (under negotiation) Central Africa.
- European Commission (201) "Economic partnership agreement with the East African community partner states (yet to be signed)". European Commission. https://agriculture.ec.europa.eu/international/agricultural-trade/bilateral-agreements/acp_en
- European Commission (Accessed November 24, 2023a) East African Community (EAC). EU trade relations with the East African Community. Facts, figures and latest developments. European Commission. Retrieved from https://policy.trade.ec.europa.eu/eu-trade-relationships-country-and-region/countries-and-regions/east-african-community-eac_en
- European Commission (May 17, 2023b). Report on the Fourth Round of Negotiations Between the European Union and Kenya for the Bilateral Implementation of the Economic Partnership Agreement with the East African Community (EAC). European Commission, Brussels. <https://circabc.europa.eu/ui/group/09242a36-a438-40fd-a7af-fe32e36cbd0e/library/0d8018ec-eac0-4692-85bc-64ddad21c754/details?download=true>
- European Commission (Accessed November 24, 2023) African, Caribbean and Pacific countries Overview of the EU's agricultural trade with African, Caribbean and Pacific countries (ACP), including trade agreements and agri-food trade statistics. Retrieved from https://agriculture.ec.europa.eu/international/agricultural-trade/bilateral-agreements/acp_en
- European Commission (2021). Interim Economic Partnership Agreement between the EU and the Central Africa Party. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/EN/legal-content/summary/interim-economic-partnership-agreement-between-the-eu-and-the-central-africa-party.html>
- European Commission (2019b) Interim Agreement with a view to an Economic Partnership Agreement between the European Community and its Member States, of the one part, and the Central Africa Party, of the other part. Official Journal of the European Union.
- Fairtrade (23 June, 2022) "Constitution of the Association". Retrieved from <https://www.fairtrade.net/about/mission>.
- Fairtrade (Accessed October 11, 2023) "Our mission and vision". Retrieved from <https://www.fairtrade.net/about/mission>
- FAO (2019a) Commission on Genetic Resources for Food and Agriculture Assessments. Rome. 572 pp. (<http://www.fao.org/3/CA3129EN/CA3129EN.pdf>) Licence: CC BY-NC-SA 3.0 IGO
- FAO (2019b) The State of the World's Biodiversity for Food and Agriculture, J. Bélanger & D. Pilling (eds.).
- FAO (2021) Strategic Framework 2022-2031. FAO Commission on Genetic Resources for Food and Agriculture Assessments. Rome. <https://www.fao.org/3/cb7099en/cb7099en.pdf>

- Feola, G., & Jaworska, S. (2019). One transition, many transitions? A corpus-based study of societal sustainability transition discourses in four civil society's proposals. *Sustainability Science*, 14, 1643-1656.
- Friedman, K., Bridgewater, P., Agostini, V., Agardy, T., Arico, S., Biermann, F., ... & Teneva, L. (2022). The CBD Post-2020 biodiversity framework: People's place within the rest of nature. *People and Nature*, 4(6), 1475-1484.
- Friends of the Earth (FoE) (2022) "Replanting Agricultural Biodiversity in the CBC". Friends of the Earth.
- Friends of the Earth (FoE)(Accessed October 20, 2023) "Who we are". Retrieved from <https://www.foei.org/who-are-friends-of-the-earth/>
- Gereffi, G., Humphrey, J., & Sturgeon, T. (2005). The governance of global value chains. *Review of international political economy*, 12(1), 78-10. Gupta, J., Liverman, D., Prodani, K., Aldunce, P., Bai, X., Broadgate, W., ... & Verburg, P. H. (2023). Earth system justice needed to identify and live within Earth system boundaries. *Nature Sustainability*, 1-9.
- Goodman, D. (2017). Agrifood studies in the 'age of ecology': nature, corporeality, bio-politics. In *The Rural* (pp. 127-148). Routledge.
- Goldberg, P. K. and Larson, G. (2023), "The Unequal Effects of Globalization", Cambridge (MA).
- GRAIN (2022) "GRAIN in 2022. Highlights of our activities." Retrieved from <https://grain.org/en/article/6968-grain-s-2022-activity-report>
- GreenPeace (Accessed October 20, 2023a) "Our Values". Retrieved from <https://www.greenpeace.org/international/about/values/>
- GreenPeace (2023b) "Greenpeace International Annual Report 2022". GreenPeace.
- Grundmann, R., & Krishnamurthy, R. (2010). The discourse of climate change: A corpus-based approach. *Critical approaches to discourse analysis across disciplines*, 4(2), 125-146.
- Hajer, M. A., & Wagenaar, H. (Eds.). (2003). *Deliberative policy analysis: understanding governance in the network society*. Cambridge University Press.
- Hamann, L., Luschnat, K., Niemuth, S., Smolarz, P., & Golombek, S. (2014). CSR in the coffee industry: Sustainability issues at Nestlé-Nespresso and Starbucks. *Journal of European Management & Public Affairs Studies*, 2(1), 31-35.
- Hickel, J., & Kallis, G. (2020). Is green growth possible?. *New political economy*, 25(4), 469-486.
- Horton, P. (2017). We need radical change in how we produce and consume food. *Food Security*, 9(6), 1323-1327.
- Howitt, R., & Suchet-Pearson, S. (2006). Rethinking the building blocks: ontological pluralism and the idea of 'management'. *Geografiska Annaler: Series B, Human Geography*, 88(3), 323-335.
- IFAD (2021) "IFAD Strategy on Diversity, Equity and Inclusion." Retrieved from <https://webapps.ifad.org/members/eb/134/docs/EB-2021-134-R-9.pdf>
- IFAD (2021) IFAD Strategy on Diversity, Equity and Inclusion. <https://webapps.ifad.org/members/eb/134/docs/EB-2021-134-R-9.pdf>
- IFAD (2022) "IFAD Strategy on Biodiversity 2022-2025." Retrieved from https://www.ifad.org/en/-/biodiversity-strategy?p_l_back_url=%2Fen%2Fpolicies-and-strategies
- IFAD (2022) IFAD Strategy on Biodiversity 2022-2025. https://www.ifad.org/en/-/biodiversity-strategy?p_l_back_url=%2Fen%2Fpolicies-and-strategies
- International Labour Organisation (ILO) (2023) "Transformative change and SDG 8: The critical role International Labour Organization (ILO) (2012), "Global Wage Report 2012/13: Wages and equitable growth", Geneva: ILO
- IPBES (2019): Global assessment report on biodiversity and ecosystem services of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services. E. S. Brondizio, J. Settele, S. Díaz, and H. T. Ngo (editors). IPBES secretariat, Bonn, Germany. 1148 pages. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3831673>
- IPCC (March 2023). "Synthesis Report Of the IPCC Sixth Assessment Report (AR6)". IPCC. Retrieved from https://report.ipcc.ch/ar6syr/pdf/IPCC_AR6_SYR_LongerReport.pdf
- IPCC (March 2023). Synthesis Report Of the IPCC Sixth Assessment Report (AR6). IPCC. https://report.ipcc.ch/ar6syr/pdf/IPCC_AR6_SYR_LongerReport.pdf
- IPCC (March 2023). Synthesis Report Of the IPCC Sixth Assessment Report (AR6). IPCC. https://report.ipcc.ch/ar6syr/pdf/IPCC_AR6_SYR_LongerReport.pdf
- IPCC. (2022). Climate Change 2022: Impacts, Adaptation, and Vulnerability. In: H.-O. Pörtner, D.C. Roberts, E.S. Poloczanska, K. Mintenbeck, M. Tignor, A. Alegría, M. Craig, S. Langsdorf, S. Lösschke, V. Möller, A. Okem (eds). Contribution of Working Group II to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, Cambridge University Press.
- Isti'annah, A., & Winarti, D. (2023). The discourse of environment in Indonesian tourism website: A corpus-assisted study. In *Reimagining Innovation in Education and Social Sciences* (pp. 179-188). Routledge.

- Jonas, T (2022) "Biodiversity COP : We are not here to re-negotiate the Convention, says IPC, slams the so-called 'nature-based solutions'" La Via Campesina. Retrieved from: <https://viacampesina.org/en/biodiversity-cop-we-are-not-here-to-re-negotiate-the-convention-says-ipc-slams-the-so-called-nature-based-solutions/>
- Karabarbounis, L. and Neiman, B. (2013), "The Global Decline of the Labor Share", *The Quarterly Journal of Economics* 129(1):61-103.
- Karousakis, K. (2022). OECD submission on Target 18 on Incentives of the post-2020 Global Biodiversity Framework.
- Kjaer, A. M. (2004). *Governance*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Lashitew, A. A. (2021). Corporate uptake of the Sustainable Development Goals: Mere greenwashing or an advent of institutional change?. *Journal of International Business Policy*, 4, 184-200.
- La Via Campesina (LVC). (2 October, 2000) "Biodiversity and Genetic Resources". (Accessed October 17, 2023). <https://viacampesina.org/en/biodiversity-and-genetic-resources12/>
- La Via Campesina (LVC). (2022) "La Via Campesina Political Declaration: 30 years of collective struggle, hope and solidarity". Retrieved from <https://viacampesina.org/en/la-via-campesina-political-declaration-30-years-of-collective-struggle-hope-and-solidarity/>
- La Via Campesina (LVC). (2023). "La Via Campesina's Annual Report". Retrieved from <https://viacampesina.org/en/annual-report-2022/>
- Lawrence, T. J., Stedman, R. C., Morreale, S. J., & Taylor, S. R. (2019). Rethinking landscape conservation: linking globalized agriculture to changes to indigenous community-managed landscapes. *Tropical Conservation Science*, 12, 1940082919889503.
- Leventon, J., Duşe, I. A., & Horcea-Milcu, A. I. (2021). Leveraging biodiversity action from plural values: transformations of governance systems. *Frontiers in Ecology and Evolution*, 9, 609853.
- LIDL (Accessed December 3rd, 2023a) "A better Tomorrow: Responsible Sourcing". <https://www.abettertomorrow-lidl-ni.co.uk/sourcing/#overview>
- LIDL (Accessed December 3rd, 2023b) "A better Tomorrow: idl develops first biodiversity standard for conventional fruit and vegetable farming". <https://www.abettertomorrow-lidl-ni.co.uk/lidl-develops-first-biodiversity-standard-for-conventional-fruit-and-vegetable-farming/>
- Marin-Burgos, V., Clancy, J. S., & Lovett, J. C. (2015). Contesting legitimacy of voluntary sustainability certification schemes: Valuation languages and power asymmetries in the Roundtable on Sustainable Palm Oil in Colombia. *Ecological economics*, 117, 303-313.
- Martín-López, B. (2021). Plural valuation of nature matters for environmental sustainability and justice. *The Royal Society*.
- McDermott, C. L. (2014). REDDuced: From sustainability to legality to units of carbon—The search for common interests in international forest governance. *Environmental Science & Policy*, 35, 12-19.
- McDermott, C. L., Montana, J., Bennett, A., Gueiros, C., Hamilton, R., Hirons, M., ... & Picot, L. (2023). Transforming land use governance: Global targets without equity miss the mark. *Environmental Policy and Governance*, 33(3), 245-257.
- McElwee, P., Fernández-Llamazares, Á., Aumeeruddy-Thomas, Y., Babai, D., Bates, P., Galvin, K., ... & Brondízio, E. S. (2020). Working with Indigenous and local knowledge (ILK) in large-scale ecological assessments: Reviewing the experience of the IPBES Global Assessment. *Journal of Applied Ecology*, 57(9), 1666-1676.
- Mcneill, J. (2020). Exporting environmental objectives or erecting trade barriers in recent EU free trade agreements. *Australian and New Zealand Journal of European Studies*, 12(1).
- Menton, M., & Gilbert, P. (2021). BINGO Complicity, Necropolitical Ecology and Environmental Defenders. *Policy Matters*, 22, 18-31.
- Nasr, C. (2023). Going Beyond the Great Divide Between Nature and Culture: The Concept of "Relocalized Society" to Account for the Local Agri-Food Networks. In: Jay Kassiola, J., Luke, T.W. (eds) *The Palgrave Handbook of Environmental Politics and Theory. Environmental Politics and Theory*. Palgrave Macmillan, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-14346-5_19
- Nespresso (August 2023) "Discover the AAA Premium Quality Sustainability Program". Nespresso. Retrieved from <https://www.sustainability.nespresso.com/communities/aaa-sustainable-quality-program>
- Nunan, F. (2018). Navigating multi-level natural resource governance: An analytical guide. In *Natural Resources Forum*, 42(3), 159-17.
- One Planet Network Sustainable Food Systems (April 2023) "Outcome Document of the 4 th Global Conference of the One Planet network's (10YFP) Sustainable Food Systems (SFS) Programme THE TRANSFORMATION WE NEED Emerging from global crises by shaping sustainable, resilient, healthy, and inclusive food systems". United Nations. https://www.oneplanetnetwork.org/sites/default/files/2023-05/Final%20outcome%20document_4th%20global%20SFSP%20conference_v28APR2023.pdf
- One Planet network Sustainable Food Systems (SFS) Programme (2020) *Towards a Common*

- One Planet network Sustainable Food Systems (SFS) Programme (2020) "Towards a Common Understanding of Sustainable Food Systems. Key approaches, concepts and terms." Retrieved from https://www.oneplanetnetwork.org/sites/default/files/from-crm/sfs_programme_glossary_towards_a_common_understanding_of_sfs_2020.pdf
- One Planet network Sustainable Food Systems (SFS) Programme (April 2023) "Outcome Document of the 4 th Global Conference of the One Planet network's (10YFP) Sustainable Food Systems (SFS) Programme THE TRANSFORMATION WE NEED Emerging from global crises by shaping sustainable, resilient, healthy, and inclusive food systems". Retrieved from https://www.oneplanetnetwork.org/sites/default/files/2023-05/Final%20outcome%20document_4th%20global%20SFSP%20conference_v28APR2023.pdf
- Pascual, U., Adams, W. M., Díaz, S., Lele, S., Mace, G. M., & Turnhout, E. (2021). Biodiversity and the challenge of pluralism. *Nature Sustainability*, 4(7), 567-572.
- Panwar, R., Ober, H., & Pinkse, J. (2023). The uncomfortable relationship between business and biodiversity: Advancing research on business strategies for biodiversity protection. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 32(5), 2554-2566.
- Parrique, T., Barth, J., Briens, F., Kerschner, C., Kraus-Polk, A., Kuokkanen, A., & Spangenberg, J. H. (2019). Decoupling debunked. Evidence and arguments against green growth as a sole strategy for sustainability. *A study edited by the European Environment Bureau EEB*.
- Peters, B. G., & Pierre, J. (2000). Citizens versus the new public manager: The problem of mutual empowerment. *Administration & Society*, 32(1), 9-28.
- Questionmark (Accessed November 27, 2023) "About". <https://www.thequestionmark.org/about>
- Rainforest Alliance (2021a) "Integrated Community Forest Management Position Paper". Retrieved from <https://www.rainforest-alliance.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/07/integrated-community-forest-management-position-paper.pdf>
- Rainforest Alliance (May 1st, 2021). "A Greener Future for Coffee Farmers: Rainforest Alliance and the Nespresso AAA Program". Rainforest Alliance. Retrieved from <https://www.rainforest-alliance.org/resource-item/lessons-learned-nespresso-aaa-sustainable-quality-program/>
- Rainforest Alliance (Accessed October 11, 2023a) "About". Retrieved from <https://www.rainforest-alliance.org/about/>
- Rainforest Alliance (Accessed October 12, 2023b) "UTZ Certification (Now Part of the Rainforest Alliance)". Retrieved from <https://www.rainforest-alliance.org/utz/>
- Roundtable on Sustainable Palm Oil (RSPO) (2018) "Code of Conduct Policy Statement – RSPO BHCV Working Group". Retrieved from <https://rspo.org/resources/?category=code-of-conduct-biodiversity-and-high-conservation-values-working-group-bhcvwg>
- Rivera-Ferre, M. G. (2018). The resignification process of Agroecology: Competing narratives from governments, civil society and intergovernmental organizations. *Agroecology and Sustainable Food Systems*, 42(6), 666-685.
- Roundtable on Sustainable Palm Oil (RSPO) (2018) "Roundtable on Sustainable Palm Oil (RSPO) Monitoring & Evaluation System: RSPO M&E Public System Report – March 2018". Retrieved from <https://rspo.org/resources/?category=guide&id=3806>
- Roundtable on Sustainable Palm Oil (RSPO) (2021) "PRACTICAL GUIDANCE ON GENDER INCLUSION AND COMPLIANCE TO THE 2018 P&C AND 2019 ISH STANDARD". Retrieved from <https://rspo.org/resources/?category=human-rights-and-social-standards-hrss>
- Slow Food (2018). "Biodiversity What is it, what does it have to do with our daily food, and what can we do to preserve it?" . Slow Food Foundation for Biodiversity. Retrieved from https://www.fondazioneSlowFood.com/wp-content/uploads/2019/04/ING_biodiversity_LR-1.pdf
- Slow Food (n.d.) "Good, Clean and Fair: the Slow Food Manifesto for Quality". Retrieved from <https://www.slowfood.com/about-us/our-philosophy/>
- Sumberg, J., Giller, K. E., & Glover, D. (2023). Evolving meanings of 'principles' in agronomic discourse. *Outlook on Agriculture*, 00307270231213659.
- Systems Change Alliance (Accessed October 18, 2023) "Going Local: Self-sufficiency Through Decentralization". Retrieved from <https://systemschangealliance.org/going-local-self-sufficiency-through-decentralization/>
- The Sustainability Consortium (TSC) (Accessed November 27, 2023a) "All Products Sustainable. Our Story". <https://sustainabilityconsortium.org/our-story/>
- The Sustainability Consortium (TSC) (Accessed November 27, 2023b) "Sustainable Coffee Challenge". <https://sustainabilityconsortium.org/project/sustainable-coffee-challenge/>
- The Sustainability Consortium (TSC) (Accessed November 27, 2023c) "Resilient Agriculture Accelerator Fund". The Sustainability Consortium (TSC) (Accessed November 27, 2023b)
- Tittonell, P., El Mujtar, V., Felix, G., Kebede, Y., Laborda, L., Luján Soto, R., & de Vente, J. (2022). Regenerative agriculture—agroecology without politics?. *Frontiers in Sustainable Food Systems*, 6, 844261.

- Tony's Chocolonely (2023a) "Our mission". <https://tonyschocolonely.com/nl/en/annual-fair-reports/annual-fair-report-2021-2022#https://tonyschocolonely.com/nl>
- Tony's Chocolonely (2023b) "Tony's Chocolonely Annual Fair Report 2021 / 2022". <https://tonyschocolonely.com/nl/en/annual-fair-reports/annual-fair-report-2021-2022>
- True Price (Accessed December 4th, 2023a) "True Price". Retrieved from <https://trueprice.org/>
- True Price (Accessed December 4th, 2023b) "About True Price". Retrieved from <https://trueprice.org/about-us/>
- UN General Assembly, (UN) (October 2015). "Transforming our world : the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, 21 October 2015, A/RES/70/1," Retrieved from: <https://www.refworld.org/docid/57b6e3e44.html> [accessed 10 October 2023]
- UN General Assembly, (October 2015). Transforming our world : the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, 21 October 2015, A/RES/70/1, Retrieved from: <https://www.refworld.org/docid/57b6e3e44.html> [accessed 10 October 2023]
- UN General Assembly, (October 2015). Transforming our world : the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, 21 October 2015, A/RES/70/1, Retrieved from: <https://www.refworld.org/docid/57b6e3e44.html> [accessed 10 October 2023]
- Understanding of Sustainable Food Systems. Key approaches, concepts and terms. https://www.oneplanetnetwork.org/sites/default/files/from-crm/sfs_programme_glossary_towards_a_common_understanding_of_sfs_2020.pdf
- Unilever (2021). "The Unilever regenerative agriculture principles with Implementation Guides 2021." Unilever (Accessed October 13, 2023). Unilever at a glance. Retrieved from <https://www.unilever.com/our-company/at-a-glance/>
- McDermott, M., Mahanty, S., & Schreckenber, K. (2013). Examining equity: a multidimensional framework for assessing equity in payments for ecosystem services. *Environmental science & policy*, 33, 416-427.
- United Nations Convention on Biological Diversity (1992) Convention on Biological Diversity. <https://www.cbd.int/doc/legal/cbd-en.pdf>
- United Nations Convention on Biological Diversity (21 August 2021) First Draft of The Post-2020 Global Biodiversity Framework. <https://www.cbd.int/doc/c/0037/8045/a67574c3f7452fd6bb56c058/wg2020-03-03-en.docx>
- United Nations Convention on Biological Diversity (26 June 2022) Glossary For The First Draft of The Post-2020 Global Biodiversity Framework. <https://www.cbd.int/doc/c/e2dd/6b6c/ea4784e9111c58d6fd787ae/wg2020-04-02-en.pdf>
- United Nations Convention on Biological Diversity (5 December 2022). Recommendation Adopted by the Working Group on The Post-2020 Global Biodiversity Framework <https://www.cbd.int/doc/recommendations/wg2020-05/wg2020-05-rec-01-en.pdf>
- United Nations Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) (1992) "Convention on Biological Diversity." Retrieved from <https://www.cbd.int/doc/legal/cbd-en.pdf>
- United Nations Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) (21 August 2021) "First Draft of The Post-2020 Global Biodiversity Framework." Retrieved from <https://www.cbd.int/doc/c/0037/8045/a67574c3f7452fd6bb56c058/wg2020-03-03-en.docx>
- United Nations Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) (26 June 2022) "Glossary For The First Draft of The Post-2020 Global Biodiversity Framework." Retrieved from <https://www.cbd.int/doc/c/e2dd/6b6c/ea4784e9111c58d6fd787ae/wg2020-04-02-en.pdf>
- United Nations Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) (5 December 2022). "Recommendation Adopted by the Working Group on The Post-2020 Global Biodiversity Framework". Retrieved from <https://www.cbd.int/doc/recommendations/wg2020-05/wg2020-05-rec-01-en.pdf>
- Wild, K., Church, A., McCarthy, D., & Burgess, J. (2013). Quantifying lexical usage: vocabulary pertaining to ecosystems and the environment. *Corpora*, 8(1), 53-79.
- Willett W, Rockström J, Loken B, et al. (2019). Food in the Anthropocene: the EAT–Lancet Commission on healthy diets from sustainable food systems. *The Lancet*. [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(18\)31788-4](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(18)31788-4).
- Willis, R. (2017). Taming the climate? Corpus analysis of politicians' speech on climate change. *Environmental Politics*, 26(2), 212-231.
- Wood, E. M. (2000). Democracia contra capitalismo: la renovación del materialismo histórico. siglo XXI.
- World Trade Organization (WTO) (2022) "Climate Change Adaptation and Trade. Policy brief." Retrieved from https://www.wto.org/english/news_e/news22_e/dgo_ted_climate_change_sept22.pdf
- World Trade Organization (WTO) (2023). "World Trade Report 2023. Re-globalization for a secure, inclusive and sustainable future". Retrieved from https://www.wto.org/english/res_e/booksp_e/wtr23_e/wtr23_e.pdf

WWF (2021). "Farming with Biodiversity. Towards nature-positive production at scale.". WWF International, Gland, Switzerland.

WWF (2022) *Living Planet Report 2022 – Building a nature positive society*. Almond, R.E.A., Grooten, M., Juffe Bignoli, D. & Petersen, T. (Eds). WWF, Gland, Switzerland.

WWF (Accessed October 19, 2023a) "What is biodiversity? What is under threat and why it matters". WWF. Retrieved from

WWF (Accessed October 19, 2023b) "About us". WWF. Retrieved from <https://www.worldwildlife.org/about/>

This project is funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement no. 101082057.